

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fLOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 5.4

REFLOW PILOT APPLICATIONS

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This deliverable reports on the prototypes developed by the six pilot cities. The main focus of this deliverable is on the technical description of the solutions developed, highlighting how they function and the technology adopted to implement them. The deliverable also documents the process that led to the development of the prototypes, namely the modelling process and its results, and any supporting tools developed in the project to facilitate prototype implementation.
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List of abbreviations and keywords

ActivityPub	ActivityPub is a standard for the Internet in the Social Web Networking Group of the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C).
API	Application programming interface
Back-end	Data access layer of a piece of software, mostly a web application in contrast to the presentation layer or front-end.
Bonfire	Current version of the back-end developed in Reflow, superseding Zenpub, the previous version.
Business process	A business process is a collection of structured activities that achieve a specific goal.
Circular Economy (CE)	A Circular Economy is an alternative to a dominant linear industrial model of design, produce, purchase, consume and dispose. A circular model aims to redefine growth and a positive societal impact. For its development a systemic approach and a deep transformation of habits and behaviour are needed. It entails a transition from using finite energy resources, to using renewable ones (designing the concept of-waste out of the system), while building economic, natural and social impact. Although starting from different materials in REFLOW, the focus of the circular economy gradually extends beyond these issues related to material management and covers other aspects such as the social impact, technological aspects and the evolution of urban governance structures. Since Circular Economy is purposive, but isn't just about sustainability environmentally and economically, the social components are fundamental for this transition to happen. This happens in mindset and cultural rituals: from the way we design, produce, consume, purchase and dispose, all the way to how we see and value existing, or even abundant, resources present in the local environments.
Co-creation	Co-creation is a product or service design process that integrates users.
Core requirement	Core requirements are requirements describing the behaviour of the economic foundation. These are the requirements for functionalities that REFLOW OS should offer and will be available for each pilot.
Data dashboard	A data dashboard is an information management tool that tracks, analyses and displays key data points.
Ecosystem	A (business) ecosystem is a network of organizations involved in the delivery of a product or service through competition and cooperation.
Economic Event	An observed economic flow in the Value Flows vocabulary. This could reflect a change in the quantity of an economic resource. It is also defined by its behaviour in relation to the economic resource.

Economic Resource	A resource that is useful to people or the ecosystem in the Value Flows vocabulary.
Foody	The name of the fruit and vegetable wholesale market in Milan, Italy.
Front-end	Front-end is the client-side or web design in the web industry
Functional requirements	Functional requirements define the required behaviour of the system to be built. They define the capabilities that a product must provide to its users. Functional requirements are based on system objectives and respond to the critical task of ensuring the right implementation of the expected functionality in the final software.
GUI	Graphical user interface
GraphQL	An open-source data query and manipulation language for APIs, and a runtime for fulfilling queries with existing data.
Intents	In Value Flows vocabulary, intents describe potential future events which have not been agreed to by other agents, such as offers and requests. Intents are often used for discovering another agent to participate in the desired event.
Levers	These are defined as practices that create the leverage to change towards circularity in cities. The circular economy levers are based on the general assumption that a small force can lead to major changes.
Material Passport	A cryptographically signed trace of all the events a resource has gone through (a resource's history), including actors and other resources present in those events.
Metadata	Metadata is structured data that contains information on characteristics of other data.
Minimum viable product (MVP)	A minimum viable product is a version of a product with just enough features to attract early users and validate a product idea early in the product development cycle.
Open data	Open data is the idea of data that can be used and redistributed by everyone for every purpose. Restrictions are only made to clarify the source or to secure the openness of the data.
Persona	A persona is a fictional character presenting a user type that might use the product. It is created based on research and helps to understand the users' needs, experiences, behaviours and goals.
Phoenix	Bonfire's default Web Graphical User Interface, a native web interface for REFLOW OS back-end.

Pilot requirement	Pilot requirements are pilot specific requirements that go beyond the economic foundation.
Requirement's elicitation	In requirements engineering, requirements elicitation is the process of collecting information to research and discover the requirements of a system.
Open Data Dashboard	A component of the Reflow architecture to provide access to the data generated, integrated and used in the context of the project.
UI	User interface
Urban metabolism	Urban metabolism can be understood as the collection of complex socio-technical and socio-ecological processes by which flows of materials, energy, people, and information shape the city, service the needs of its populace, and impact the surrounding hinterland.
Use case	A use case gathers possible scenarios of interactions between an actor and a system to achieve a business goal.
User requirement	User requirements describe what needs a user has when using a system, e.g., which activities the user must be able to perform.
User stories	A user story is a tool often used in Agile software development, describing a feature of the software from the end user's perspective. As user stories clearly state the different types of users, what they desire and why they can be seen as a very high-level definition of requirements.
Value Flows	A set of common vocabularies to describe flows of economic resources of all kinds within distributed economic ecosystems. The core is based on the REA (Resource, Event, Agent) ontology. The purpose is to enable internetworking among many different software projects for resource planning and accounting within fractal networks of people and groups. In graphics agents are represented in green, economic resources in blue, and economic events in grey.

1 Introduction

1.1 About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualize and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project provides best practices aligning market and government needs in order to create favourable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assess their social, environmental and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

1.2 REFLOW Vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to **social, environmental and economic impact**; where **technology** is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and support resilience of social and ecological systems; where **governance** is collaborative and inclusive; where **knowledge** is shared, and **stakeholders** are active and involved.

1.3 About the deliverable

This deliverable reports the work done in the scope of Task 5.4 “REFLOW OS Pilot Applications Development and Testing”. The focus of this document is the technical development carried out by the pilot cities and the process that has been followed to facilitate the pilots’ technical activities.

Because of this focus, the scope of the deliverable is restricted to what is relevant from a technical point of view. Background information about why particular use cases have been chosen by the pilots, as well as the context and different activities that have taken place in the pilot cities are described in other deliverables, which are referred to from the present text.

Although we have attempted to write the deliverable in a language that is understandable for the general public, the document also strives to be concrete and therefore contains references to technical tools and formalisms, either developed within the project or available in the public domain. A list of abbreviations and keywords is presented at the beginning of this document.

1.4 Structure of the report

The deliverable starts by presenting the task's goals and the context in which the task took place, together with the different types of prototypes that have been developed (Chapter 2). It then explains the development process and why this process has been adopted (Chapter 3).

Subsequently, it describes the supporting tools that have been developed in the project to support the implementation of the use cases (Chapter 4). The main subject of this deliverable are the pilot prototypes, which are described in Chapter 5. Finally, the last chapter discusses some lessons learnt and presents conclusions.

2 Task 5.4 description

2.1 Task 5.4 goals

The goal of T5.4 was primarily to experiment with concrete and innovative solutions that rethink existing productive systems and make them more circular and resource efficient.

Across the six pilot cities, a variety of actors and stakeholders have been involved in this process, such as Fablabs, municipalities, citizens, local public and private organisations. This document presents the results that this process has led to.

Each prototype has been developed to target a specific resource in a particular local situation. Because of the diversity of local situations and resources targeted, the prototypes are quite different from each other.

Therefore, the use of technology (hardware and software) also varies considerably, as it will be explained in the following sections. Some pilots have used technology as a fundamental part in implementing circular solutions, while for other pilots technology has been used to provide more concrete examples to support a discussion on circular economy. Each prototype, in any case, uses one or more tools developed in WP2.

2.2 Relation to other tasks

With respect to the Reflow Framework described in D1.3, the prototypes developed in Task 5.4 are positioned at the "Product and tech innovation" level (FIGURE 1) and their technical realisation have been supported by the work of WP2.

FIGURE 1: THE REFLOW FRAMEWORK

Considering the Circular Economy levers identified in the Reflow Framework (levers, when activated, drive change towards economic circularity), the ones that are most relevant for this task are in the Operational Dimension, namely “Prototyping and experimentation” and “Data and tech”.

Further, the process that has led to the development of Reflow’s prototypes (selection of the solution, co-design and co-creation together with the stakeholders, governance and business perspectives) has been supported by the work of Reflow’s Work Packages: mainly WP3 for the Material Flow Analysis, WP4 with the tools from the Collaborative Governance Toolkit, WP6 for capacity building and WP7 for the business models.

This task has a close relation to T5.3, which has been carried out in parallel with the present task. The starting points for both tasks are taken from the plans of the pilots in terms of activities, as reported in each pilot’s Theory of Change (see D1.4), as well as the Material Flow Analysis carried out in WP3.

T5.3 and T5.4 are quite interrelated: both tasks have focused on the same use-cases. T5.3 has provided a broader context for T5.4, by performing the following for each use-case selected by T5.4:

- An analysis on how to make the loops (more) circular
- An analysis of what levers from the REFLOW Framework to use
- A mapping of the stakeholders (potentially) involved in making the use case (more) circular

Conversely, T5.4 has provided detailed modelling and concrete experimentation of the use-cases. The information gained by these activities has made T5.3's analysis more precise and more relevant for each pilot, because it was about something each pilot was actively pursuing.

This task also contributed to the section "Toolkit in Practice" of D4.4 Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit, by providing information about the technological solutions developed. Finally, given that technology can be also used as a tool for citizen engagement, this task is also related to T5.5 "Citizen Engagement and Capacity Building Strategies". More concretely, developing digital solutions can help citizens understand material flows and foster circular economy initiatives, as it will be discussed in D5.5.

2.3 Type of prototypes

When looking at the materials each pilot city has focussed on, we can distinguish two categories:

- Tangible materials (such as Textile, Plastic, Wood, Food)
- "Intangible" resources (such as Energy)

The first category contains "materials" that have a clear identity (such as a plastic candy box) and can therefore be identified by an id. A track & trace system can therefore monitor the ids of the materials during the process the materials undergo. At each step of the process, the monitoring system can read the id to update the track & trace information.

On the contrary, the second category is predominantly dealt with in terms of measurements of quantity, such as a litre of water or a Kilowatt of energy. This implies that monitoring the flow of such resources is not based on ids, as the system cannot read the id of what moves in the process under consideration. To monitor such flows, one needs to have access to the measurements of the quantities as they move, for example, from production to usage points. For the two pilots that deal with energy (and therefore with "intangible" resources), measuring it at different points was either not possible (because of how the energy supply works at the national level) or not the focus of the prototype.

Therefore, we can classify the pilot cities' prototypes into two groups. The first one models and measures the flow of the chosen tangible material (i.e., textile, plastic, wood and food). The second one models and measures the intangible material (electric and heat energy) at the point of usage, and therefore examines more a snapshot of the material quantity over time rather than a flow.

This has led to a different use of WP2 tools for the implemented prototypes: cities dealing with a "flow" (Amsterdam, Milan, Paris and Vejle) have primarily used the track and trace functionality from REFLOW OS, while cities dealing with a "snapshot" (Berlin and Cluj-Napoca) have used primarily the visualisation capabilities of the Open Data Dashboard.

3 Development Process

This chapter described the approach we followed in developing Reflow's prototypes, and why it was necessary or more effective to proceed this way.

3.1 Approach

As described in Reflow's technical deliverables such as D2.4, D2.5 and the upcoming D2.6, Reflow's tools use a standard called Value Flows¹, which is a formally defined vocabulary to model resource flows. In particular, REFLOW OS, and specifically the back-end part and the concept interface Weloop, have been developed in collaboration with the Value Flows community.

Value Flows is a relatively young standard that is still being modified as a result of applying it to new use cases. In fact, some modifications have been the direct result of discussions generated around Reflow use cases (for example, see the discussion at <https://github.com/dyne/reflow-os/issues/3>), which contribute to the impacts generated by Reflow.

On the other hand, this has implied that it was not clear from the beginning what the correct way was (according to Value Flows) to model each particular resource flow the pilots were focussing on. Sometimes the "correct" way was decided discussing with the members of the Value Flows community on their Gitter channel^[6].

In order to develop the prototypes, we have adopted a phased approach where some developer teams from the pilots started to experiment with Value Flows and WP2 tools with the goal to "open the path" for the other pilots. We wanted to avoid the risk of having multiple pilots be blocked by the same technical issues or modelling dilemmas. This approach was more relevant to pilots using REFLOW OS and Weloop, as those are the components depending more on Value Flows, while the Open Data Dashboard does not have this dependency (or to a much lesser extent, as it will be described in D2.6).

The practical goal of this approach was to generate a library of validated models, code examples and tools that other pilots could adopt to reduce their development time in implementing their technical solutions. Furthermore, this curated REFLOW OS "onboarding" collection of resources for developers is set to be an important contribution in the future for the adoption of REFLOW OS by the technical community.

The tools will be described in the following section, while the resulting models will be described in the corresponding section of the pilot use case they model.

¹ Value Flows, a vocabulary for the distributed economic networks of the next economy, <https://www.valueflo.ws/>

4 Supporting tools

This section describes the tools that were developed in order to facilitate the modelling of the use cases according to Value Flows and the testing of the tools provided by WP2, in particular the REFLOW OS back-end (Bonfire).

4.1 Graphic modelling tool

Concretely, in order to use the functionality of REFLOW OS, a pilot had to model their use case according to the Value Flows vocabulary. This meant expressing their material flows in terms of Resources, Events and Agents. Pilots initially chose to use graphical tools such as Miro in order to do so.

Expressing a model in a graphical way has the advantage to easily communicate to the viewer the entire picture at a glance as well as the details when zooming in. However, it also has some disadvantages:

- A picture is more difficult to modify compared to a text (for example, if you want to change each occurrence of a particular agent name in another agent name)
- Pictures are more difficult to version when you want to keep track of the changes, like it is possible with software
- It is difficult to enforce a homogeneous layout and usage of graphical symbols (in this case, the symbols and positioning for resources, events and agents) when several different authors produce the diagrams.

For these reasons, the Amsterdam pilot developed a tool² that allows to specify a flow in a textual format, based on specifying:

- The agents participating in the flow
- The resources present in the flow
- The events that compose the flow, each with the agent performing them and the agent's role
- Logically grouping the agents, resources and events in sub-graphs.

² Available at <https://github.com/reflow-project/Amsterdam-pilot/tree/main/graphviz>

An example of this textual specification, which is written in the Ruby programming language, is the following (shortened for clarity):

```
graph("IsolationGowns") {
# Model the use cycles and recycle rates of rfid-tagged isolation gowns

#use cycle
sub_graph("Use Cycle") do

# Define the agents
agent :a_hospital, "Hospital"
agent :a_laundry, "Laundry Service"
agent :a_tsc, "Textile Service Company"

# Define the resources
resource :r_gown_dirty, "Gown Lot (dirty)"
resource :r_gown_dirty2, "Gown Lot (dirty)"
resource :r_gown_clean, "Gown Lot (clean)"
...

# Define the events
event :e_pickup, "Transfer (pickup)"
event :e_work, "Work (laundry)"
event :e_pickup_tcs, "Transfer"
...

# Define which agent is involved in each event and with what role
role :e_pickup, :a_hospital, "provider"
role :e_pickup, :a_laundry, "receiver"
role :e_work, :a_laundry, "performer"
...
# Define the flow in terms of resources (:r_...) and events (:e_...)
flow [:r_gown_dirty,:e_pickup,:r_gown_dirty2,:e_work,:r_gown_clean, ...]
end

sub_graph("Sorting and Incineration") do
# define another cycle: sorting and incineration
...
end

sub_graph("Production flow") do
# define another cycle: production flow
...
end
}
```

When processed by the script, the following picture (FIGURE 2) in PNG format of the three flows specified in the text is automatically generated (again, shortened for visibility):

FIGURE 2

In this diagram, events are represented as grey squares with rounded corners, resources as blue squares, and agents as green circles. Additionally, each agent is connected to an event with an edge which also provides a label indicating what the role of an agent is by the event. This is necessary since events sometimes have more agents associated with them, in the role of provider or receiver.

4.2 Script-based flow simulation tool

While the tool described above is meant to support the modelling phase of a pilot use case development, the Amsterdam pilot has also developed a command-line tool that can generate data to feed into REFLOW OS, also based on a textual description of the resource flow. The goal of this tool is twofold:

- Test whether the model created at the previous step is correct, by generating resources, agents and events and uploading this data to the REFLOW OS back-end. In other words, concretely verifying whether the model matches with how REFLOW OS works and, therefore, with the assumptions implicitly defined by the developers of the back-end (Dyne).
- Test the system for bugs and inconsistencies, by generating simulated data that can scale in quantity and type of flow represented.

Both goals have largely contributed to the understanding of how to model the pilots' use-cases with Value Flows, as well as to debug the tools developed by WP2 tools. As already mentioned, concretely implementing use-cases in Value Flows has also led to many interactions with the Value Flows community, and to changes to that standard as a consequence of those discussions, which in fact can be considered as another contribution of the project.

Concretely, the tool is written in the Ruby programming language, and defines a language, analogously to the previous one, to specify a flow. The natural evolution of these two tools would be to unify these languages, but at the moment, they are different since the simulation requires much more details about each event than the graphic display of the flow.

The simulated flow is executed by performing each event according to the event schedule specified in the language.

An example of the events with their scheduling is the following:

```
# every day (cron:1) between 5 and 10 (rand(5..10)) in-use gowns are put in the hamper
event :e_out_use, "Use (Discard)" do
  schedule cron: 1
  process do
    as_performer :a_hospital
    pool_take :gown_in_use, rand(5..10)
    use_batch "used in emergency room"
    pool_put :gown_dirty_pool
  end
end

# every seven days (cron:7) the entire dirty pool is picked up
event :e_transfer_pickup, "pickup" do
  schedule cron: 7
  process do
    as_performer :a_hospital
    pool_take :gown_dirty_pool
    pack_container :gown_dirty_container
    transfer_container :gown_dirty_container, :a_hospital, :a_launderer
  end
end
```

The script will run and produce for every day included in the simulation the event scheduled:

```
2022-02-07: processing event: e_out_use
created (use) process: 01FVABRE62WFTR61BH5PG9WAVT
Created REFLOW OS Use event: 01FVABRHZG41Q40G6WEC3Y7FWS
Created REFLOW OS Use event: 01FVABRPQ1K159CKRTM1XJDA3K
Created REFLOW OS Use event: 01FVABRSWXTV0ZH7VPBSN7XAX2
...
```

At the end a summary of the resources is presented:

CONTAINERS

```
gown_dirty_container: 18
gown_clean: 0
```



```
gown_ready_for_use: 0
POOLS
gown_in_use: 2 (a_hospital)
gown_dirty_pool: 0 (a_hospital)
INVENTORIES
gown_stock: 8 (a_tsc)
```

As already mentioned, the possibility to quickly modify the flow and test the system has been of great help for the development of REFLOW OS.

4.3 Graphic-based flow simulation tool

Together with the above-mentioned command-line tool, the Milan and Amsterdam pilots have collaborated to create a more visually oriented tool, in order to cater for different types of developers, i.e., the more visually oriented or more command-line oriented ones.

This tool is based on Node-RED³, a browser-based platform geared to support IoT applications. Node-RED can be best explained by introducing a screenshot (FIGURE 3) representing how it is used in the project:

³ <https://nodered.org/>

FIGURE 3: NODE-RED WEB INTERFACE

The picture represents the HTTP endpoints defined in Node-RED (the blocks called “Form”), that can be called using a HTTP call with parameters to execute the pipeline connected to each endpoint. The functionality implemented by the different endpoints encapsulates basic operations to perform against REFLOW OS, such as logging in a user, defining locations and unity of measures, creating resources, processes and events.

These endpoints are used as a building block to define a flow. A script can call them in a particular order to upload data to REFLOW OS. This has been extensively used to rapidly prototype flows that served as concrete examples in defining the format for the Material Passport, which is the cryptographically signed record of all the transactions a particular resource has gone through (for more info see D2.4 and D2.5).

An example of such a flow is defined in `doFlow.sh`⁴ and can be summarized as follows:

```
Log in user hospital and the gown owner (who is also the cleaner)
Define units of measurements and locations
Create resources: soap and water (to wash the gowns), cotton (to sew the gown)
Consume the cotton to produce a gown
```

⁴ <https://github.com/reflow-project/Node-red/blob/main/doFlow.sh>

Transfer the gown to be used at the hospital
Use the gown and therefore make it dirty
Transport the gown back to the cleaner
Clean the gown consuming soap and water

This simple flow is already enough to base concrete discussions on how the Material Passport had to be defined.

5 Pilot Prototypes

In this chapter we present the prototypes developed by the pilots in the project, describing what the prototypes do, the technology used to implement them, how the prototypes were tested, and finally the resources available to use and/or reproduce the technology.

The description in this deliverable focuses on the technical implementation; for details on each prototype's context and motivation please look at D1.4.

For each of the pilot cities' prototypes, a description is provided according to the following template:

Description of functionality

- Short description of the need and the actors in this scenario
- What does the prototype do?
- If applicable, the use-case value flows schema implemented or modelled by the prototype
- How does a user use it?
- Visualisations of the prototype if available

Technical description

- What are the technical building blocks? For the front-end and the back-end, or for the touchpoints, software and in case hardware.
- How are Reflow WP2 tools used?
- If applicable, what supporting tools from the Tools chapter above have been used?

Testing

- How has the prototype been tested?
- By whom?
- What are the experiences of the users involved in testing it?

Resources

- Where is the code?
- Where, if possible, can the prototype be tested?
- What is needed to use it?

5.1 Amsterdam pilot

Amsterdam has two prototypes, the Swapshop and the Isolation gowns.

5.1.1 Swapshop prototype

The Swapshop is a shop for second-hand clothes where customers can bring their clothes to be swapped with other clothes. The application built for this use-case allows the Swapshop to keep track of the items that are sold to customers, even when the items leave the shop and possibly return later on.

The main reasons to track the items are:

- After being chosen by a customer, an item might return to the shop to be swapped again. The Swapshop wants to be able to detect this, in order to understand how second-hand clothes circulate, i.e., how they are swapped, used, and recycled.
- The Swapshop wants to get insights on the motivation of its customers: why does somebody decide to swap an item? How long does it take before an item is swapped? Etc.
- The Swapshop wants to associate a story to each item, so that a piece of cloth represents more than the mere object for a potential customer, in the hope that this changed perception will contribute to prolong the lifetime of the garment.

This prototype has been developed in close collaboration with the owners of the Swapshop, and consists of a web-based application and a Telegram bot.

The process starts when an item enters the Swapshop for the first time, and it is sorted by the Swapshop staff, who stitch a QR code onto the item. Scanning this QR code with a smartphone leads to a web page containing information about the item, which is initially empty (see [FIGURE 4](#)).

FIGURE 4

On that page, a link invites the new owner of the item (or the Swapshop staff on their behalf) to talk to the Swapbot using Telegram (see left part of FIGURE 5).

FIGURE 5

Once the user clicks on the @swapbot link (and has Telegram installed on their phone), Telegram is launched and opens in a chat with the bot. After the user chooses to start the conversation, the bot asks some questions to get information about the item (see FIGURE 5 in the middle), such as:

- What kind of garment is it?
- What model is it? What colour is the item? What is the size of the item? What is the brand? What is the material?
- Would you like to add a personal memory about this item? (e.g., a special occasion, sentimental value or bought in a special place)
- When and where did you purchase this item?
- Approximately how long and how often have you worn this item? When was the last time you wore this item?
- What message do you want to give to the new carrier?
- Do you want to add a photo? Do you want this to be seen on the website?

If the user chooses so, the information entered is displayed on the web-page (see FIGURE 5 on the right).

The bot also interacts with the user (if the user opts in for this) after this first initial contact. After that, anytime the QR code label is scanned, the bot is started from the item on the web-page. The bot then asks whether the user has swapped, worn, repaired the item, or any other action that the user has carried out on the item. After an editorial control (see FIGURE 6 in the middle), this new information is added to the web-page, as part of the narrative about that garment.

FIGURE 6

On the back-end side, all the tracking information is saved in REFLOW OS (see FIGURE 7, where we visualise the resource using Phoenix⁵, Bonfire's native interface).

FIGURE 7

In order to be able to enter information to track each item, the use case flow has been modelled with Value Flows, using the tool mentioned in section "Graphic modelling tool" (see FIGURE 8 below):

⁵ <https://www.phoenixframework.org/>

FIGURE 8⁶

In the figure three blocks are visible: the top block models the flow of items when they are in the Swapshop, get swapped and are owned by a Swapshop customer, who can bring them back to the shop, wear them or repair them.

The middle flow is when the items are not wearable anymore, and they are discarded and incinerated. The bottom flow represents when they are given to a sorting company in an attempt to recycle them back to raw materials (i.e., fibres). After this process, they can end up eventually at a textile company if this operation is successful, or they get incinerated if it is not possible to use them as fibres.

Although this use case has modelled the complete life-cycle of the second-hand clothes, at the moment, the prototype can only trace the top-most flow.

Technically, the application is composed by a Ruby-on-rails web-application that implements the web-pages containing each item’s information and a Telegram bot written in Ruby that implements the dialogue with the customers and uploads the results of the dialogue to the web application mentioned above. The latter is also responsible for uploading the data to REFLOW OS using GraphQL APIs.

This prototype is currently being tested with a group of about 25 customers selected by the Swapshop. The results will be reported in later deliverables.

⁶ The picture can be viewed at <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/reflow-project/Amsterdam-pilot/main/graphviz/swapshop.png>

The code is at <https://github.com/reflow-project/Amsterdam-pilot/tree/main/swapshop> and it is deployed on <http://reflow.the-swapshop.com/>.

To use the prototype, one needs to scan a QR code stitched to an item. An example of a web-page can be seen at <http://reflow.the-swapshop.com/code/RP00017>, from where the swapbot can be run as described above.

5.1.2 Isolation gowns prototype

This use case originated in the domain of medical isolation gowns, where it is common use, and in many cases mandatory, that if a patient is treated, the nurse wears an isolation gown to protect them from contamination (for example from COVID). It is also common practice that this gown is discarded after every single use to avoid cross contamination. Millions of these disposable gowns are being used only once and then thrown away after every single use, to be subsequently incinerated.

To solve this problem, a consortium of stakeholders including members of the Reflow Amsterdam pilot city have designed a reusable isolation gown, which is currently being produced and will be tested until the end of 2023.

One of the members of this consortium is an industrial partner which has the role of a so-called textile service provider. This role refers to a company that owns the isolation gowns, delivers them to the hospitals and collects them for washing and quality control.

This company uses its own proprietary system to keep track of the gowns through the different steps of the process, when they are delivered to the hospitals, when they are brought back, inspected for quality, washed and then shipped again if not discarded.

While the gowns are traced while they are in use, no information is known about them from the moment they are discarded. This information is also very difficult to find, because the Amsterdam pilot does not have a partner that traces the discarded gowns and can report on these figures.

This is the reason why the Amsterdam pilot decided to build a simulation based on the information provided by the above-mentioned company and by other domain experts. The goal was to generate data as realistically as possible, in order to show the potential of a tracking tool (REFLOW OS) if the real data were available. This is a common situation where, especially companies, are not willing to share their data with other stakeholders, particularly if they are competitors. Having a system that is open-source, preserves privacy and is cryptographically secure (and possibly ran by an independent entity), such as REFLOW OS, can make it easier to obtain this data.

Simulating the data can therefore be a means to gain interest from the stakeholders without suffering from the cold-start problem to have no data and therefore nothing to show.

With these in mind, the Amsterdam pilot modelled three phases of the gown’s life-cycle (with the tool explained in section [OBJ]“Graphic modelling tool”), see FIGURE 9 below⁷

FIGURE 9

The top flow describes the flow of the isolation gowns while they are in use (i.e., used in the hospital, washed, etc.). The middle flow models (analogously to the Swapshop model) the case of sorting and incineration. Finally, the bottom flow models the recycling process, when the gowns are reduced to raw material, which is used to make other gowns (this is also analogous to the Swapshop case).

These flows have been implemented in a Ruby script, which allows to specify the number of gowns taking part in the simulation and the scheduling of the flow events involving them (how many gowns are involved in each event, how often an event happens, with what delay from a previous event). Once these settings are specified, the script simulates over the course of n days (also a parameter to be set) the events and how they affect the gowns, and uploads each event to REFLOW OS.

The script is not meant to be used by a generic user, but it is directed at experts that can model the flow and stakeholders that are interested in seeing the results of possible scenarios, such as “what happens to the quantity of gowns in use if we assume 100 wash cycles before discarding and a percentage of 5% of recycling of the discarded gowns”.

To facilitate this analysis, the Open Data Dashboard can load the data from the simulation to produce a flow diagram (a Sankey diagram), see FIGURE 10 below:

⁷ Latest version available at https://gitlab.waag.org/code/reflow_amsterdam/-/raw/main/graphviz/output.png

Amsterdam/Zorgshorten/GownCyclicSankey

Amsterdam/Zorgshorten/GownSankey - Select TimeFrame

TIME RANGE

2022-02-06 < col < 2022-03-06

APPLY

FIGURE 10: INITIAL SANKEY DIAGRAM FOR THE ISOLATION GOWN USE CASE

The picture is provided by the ODD (functionality still in development) and is based on the simulation data generated by the script mentioned above. In it one can see the flow of gowns while they are in use in a given time frame, between CleanLease Eindhoven where the gowns are checked for quality control, OLVG the hospital where they are used, and CleanLease Zoetermeer where they are washed. At the moment the Sankey diagram displays the number of gowns that move between the different locations in a particular time range, keeping track of every transfer event recorded by the script during the simulation. Therefore, the same gowns are possibly counted more than once, since what we are plotting is actually their movements. We are investigating also other ways to display the gowns flow.

Technically, the script is written in Ruby and calls REFLOW OS GraphQL API interface to upload the data into REFLOW OS. As mentioned before, this script has also been used to test REFLOW OS in the early stage of its development, as explained in section “Script-based flow simulation tool”.

The prototype has been developed in strict contact with the domain experts in the Amsterdam Reflow team and also through visiting the site of the textile service provider company to understand how to model their part of the gown processing.

The code is available at <https://github.com/reflow-project/Amsterdam-pilot/tree/main/sim>. Running the code requires either a local deployment of REFLOW OS or the availability of a public node where the user is authorised to create accounts (which are the agents in the simulated flows).

5.2 Berlin pilot

5.2.1 Wastewater heat prototype

The Waste Water Heat Radar (WWHR) is a matchmaking platform which indicates excess heat energy (energy supply) and links it to buildings and districts which are in need of heat energy (energy demand). The excess energy is contained in the waste water itself and can be extracted and used with heat exchangers at dedicated locations. The platform is designed as a web application and runs smoothly in a web browser.

The main task of the application is to create awareness, show heat potentials, and foster a wider range of implementations in Berlin, in particular by accumulating inquiries and creating synergies on a district level. The image below (FIGURE 11) shows the main view of the application.

FIGURE 11: THE WASTE WATER HEAT RADAR MAIN VIEW

The main reasons for the importance of the application are:

- **Much of the energy from wastewater is not used:** In Berlin, only a small fraction of the potential energy from wastewater is used. Most of the energy remains unused and vanishes.
- **Energy from Wastewater is CO₂-neutral:** Heat from wastewater counts as CO₂-neutral, since it uses already generated energy from existing sources.
- **Energy from wastewater is linear thermal energy:** The water temperature in sewer systems is mostly season independent and can be used throughout the whole year.
- **A matching is possible:** Matching accumulated heat demands at the block or district level with potential heat supplies can be done on a large scale and for many cities.

- **The technology is well established, what is missing is a streamlined process for implementation:** The technology of heat exchangers is increasingly common, which makes a rollout possible. The bottleneck is a streamlined comprehensive process and a secure management of the critical infrastructure.

The prototype has been developed by four partners: Fraunhofer FOKUS (FOKUS), Prototypes for Europe e.V (P4E), MCS Datalabs (MCS) and Berlin's water utility company Berliner Wasserbetriebe (BWB).

The Berlin Pilot is not interested in tracing how the heat is transferred to wastewater, but they focus on calculating the available heat energy from wastewater. Therefore, they are using more dashboard-oriented tools, as mentioned in section "Type of prototypes".

Nevertheless, it is important to describe the parties involved and to describe the process on how heat from wastewater can be used with the web application. The importance lies on the flow of data that is created in order to make use of the heat energy potential.

The user of the application counts as one actor. This is typically one of the stakeholders like an urban planner, industry expert or manager of industrial sites. They use the website to retrieve information from and provide information to the platform.

Another actor in this scenario is the Berlin consortium who runs and manages the web application. The consortium itself provides and displays important information and acts as a contact point to start the implementation process. The web application processes and displays information about important infrastructure supply and demand data, coming from multiple public and private sources as well as from the user of the application (user input). A third actor is BWB as a company and infrastructure provider who accompanies the implementation process (i.e., the actual installation of a heat pump to recover the energy) once a match has been made and a user is seeking additional information to continue the implementation process.

The following graphic shows the actors, the datasets available and the flow of information, as also discussed further:

Data Flow Overview - Waste Water Heat Radar

FIGURE 12: DATA FLOW - WASTE WATER HEAT RADAR ALL INPUT AND DATA SOURCES

The prototype is a fully functional web application that displays the heat potential and heat demand for specific areas in Berlin on a per-building scale.

Data Sources

In order to understand the functionality of the application it is necessary to first discuss the different sources of data sets used in the functional prototype.

- The map: The application uses an instance of the open-source map “open street maps” for displaying and georeferencing all necessary information.
- Parcels, addresses / coordinates: Another open-source data set, directly from the Berlin Senate, is used to add information on the parcels, exact addresses as well as information about the building status (public or private building). This data set is called and referred to as ALKIS-data set.
- GIS-based data set about Wastewater Heat Potential (supply side): the wastewater heat potential is the most critical data set for the application, and it is provided by the Berlin water utility company, BWB. A complex calculation and simulation based on data from the sewer network (which itself is using the ALKIS data set), data from the wastewater pressure pipe network and data from the wastewater infrastructure forms the foundation for calculating and simulating the potential heat capacity for the entire city of Berlin. This data is both proprietary to BWB and critical data that cannot be easily shared publicly. Nonetheless, the application can also be fully functional by using a slightly randomized data set. This will ensure a fully functional prototype to demonstrate the functionality while maintaining the protection of information of critical infrastructure.
- Heat demand (demand side): a data set about heat demands on a per-building level has been simulated for certain areas in Berlin. This allows the application to be fully tested and to demonstrate the functionality, as well as guarantee a proper level of accuracy when the application will allow public requests. Each of the selected buildings has been simulated in four variations, based on different

renovation statuses of each building. Taken into consideration for the simulation was, among many factors, the ALKIS data set, as well as the type of building based on its primary usage.

- Estimated construction sites (BWB): to further increase the likelihood of the implementation of heat exchangers, the web-application additionally offers information on dates for known estimated construction plans (renovations, maintenance, etc.). This can speed up the process for implementation.

General functionality

The current prototype provides a general map of Berlin showing buildings and other important landmarks. Also, the randomized potential heat data layer is shown by default, and it can be either displayed or hidden. The user can access all functions from the main menu of the application. All functions of the prototype will be explained in detail in the following sections.

Search function

Single location

The current prototype allows for searching of addresses either by typing in an address or by uploading a file containing multiple addresses. The address can be typed into the search field in the top left corner of the application or if uploading a file, the file needs to be in CSV format, containing the full addresses of interest. When an address is searched for, the heat energy potential (supply) of the given address will be directly matched with the simulated energy consumption (demand) of the building belonging to the given address and the result will be shown in the map (FIGURE 13).

FIGURE 13: WWHR - THE ATTRIBUTE TABLE PER BUILDING

This feature works for both a single address and multiple addresses (see FIGURE 14 below).

FIGURE 14: WWHR - UPLOADING CSV FILE CONTAINING MULTIPLE ADDRESSES

Location with radius

The power of the application is revealed when a radius is added while searching for an address (see Figure 15 below). By doing so, the web application sums up all surrounding heat energy demands (Σ demands) within the set radius and compares it to the given energy potential (supply) for that location.

FIGURE 15: WWHR - SETTING A RADIUS AROUND A SPECIFIC LOCATION

This means that the application precisely calculates which percentage of the heat demand can be covered by the potential heat energy from waste water (see Figure 16 below).

FIGURE 16: WWHR - VIEW OF FOUR RENOVATION STATUSES FOR A SPECIFIC BUILDING AND SURROUNDING BUILDINGS

Filter function

The Application allows for categorization of all buildings in Berlin according to the buildings' estimated usage and heat demand (see Figure 17 below). Based on the ALKIS data set and heat simulations, 18 different categories were developed and can be accessed from the dropdown menu on the top right side of the screen.

FIGURE 17: WWHR - SETTING FILTER; CATEGORIZING BUILDINGS BY HEAD USAGE

Mark interest

Once an address is selected, a user can express interest for a specific building by entering their email address and “flagging” the building (Figure 16, bottom of pop-up window). All interests will be shown on the map. This

important feature helps to create a network of interests and fosters the movement towards using excess heat from wastewater.

Users input heat demand

Additionally, users will be able to insert their own heat demand (in kW), once an address is selected. These values can be used for a more precise matchmaking, to verify the simulations and will enable a large-scale collection of heat demand data.

Direct Contact to BWB

As described above, one of the main pain points with using heat from waste water is the lack of a streamlined process for the implementation of heat exchangers. Therefore, the web application offers the possibility to reach partners directly through the web interface, while directly providing the necessary information (address, heat demand) per location. This reduces time and fosters more inquiries.

User interaction

The user types in an address in the top left corner of the screen or alternatively uploads a CSV file containing one or multiple addresses. Optionally, when entering a single address, the user can set a radius to summarize all surrounding heat demands. Both, the potential heat capacity and heat demand for that location will be queried and matched in the background, and the results will be presented to the user in the map, in a dedicated attribute window. The user can now inspect the result and perform multiple actions:

- The user can view the potential heat capacity (kW) in a specific location as well as an estimated heat demand (kW) for that building. If a radius was chosen, the accumulated heat demand (kW) will also be shown. Furthermore, the percentage to which the building can use the heat from waste water will be shown. This percentage is particularly interesting when looking at surrounding buildings by using the radius function.
- The user can then express interest in a building. An email will be sent to the project partners, notifying them that someone has marked interest for a specific building and submitting the inserted user heat demand (kW). These values can then be compared to the simulated values (kW) and matched to the potential heat capacity (kW) available in that address.
- A user can also apply the filter function by choosing one or more categories from the dropdown menu on the top right side of the screen. All relevant buildings will be highlighted in the map and the user can freely navigate around the map to inspect the neighbourhood.

WWHR: EXPLANATORY VIDEO⁸

Apart from the map, the user can select the Open Data Dashboard (described in D2.4 and in the upcoming D2.6) from the menu (see Figure 18 below). The ODD runs independently from the map, and gives the user an overview of important information related to the topic of waste water heat in Berlin. The user can get information about heat potentials in specific districts, information about the utilized potential, the maximum potential in kW and other valuable insights. The ODD runs with individual models that can be easily added and modified in the front-end to quickly adjust to the user's needs.

⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6_2VUhQoIMo

FIGURE 18: THE OPEN DATA DASHBOARD (ODD)

Help page

In the event that a user has difficulties using the web application, a help page has been created to guide the user through the usage of said application. Additionally, a description of all layers and displayed information can be found there.

Outlook: Further Planned Features

Inquiries processing: With further development of the prototype, collecting, storing and processing full inquiries within the application is planned.

Additional data: the prototype provides a solid foundation for adding other data sets of interest, to create synergies with other energy sources (sector coupling) as well as for adding economical cost calculations to the platform itself. Among others, the following datasets are of interest:

- **Cooling demands:** One fascinating aspect of heat from waste water is that the energy can be used throughout the entire year. In the winter, the heat can be used for heating, but in the summertime the “heat” (around 15° C) can be used for cooling buildings. A comprehensive data set of cooling demands of certain buildings could therefore add to the functionality of the app and further foster the energy from wastewater
- **Data layer of energy suppliers (proprietary information):** Another highly interesting data layer is the Berlin-wide actual, and comprehensive heating demand information, which are confidential and owned by Berlin’s energy suppliers. Same confidentiality concerns apply here, yet this data set would further improve the accuracy and importance of the web-application.
- **Data layer of district heating network (proprietary information):** To create further synergies, a data layer of all functional and planned district heating networks could be included in the application. Discussions about this data set are already in early stages with Berlin’s largest energy supplier

- **Building lease (Berlin Senate, confidential):** One interesting, yet highly confidential data set is comprehensive information about property owners of buildings and sites. This could speed up the process by proactively reaching out to possible stakeholders and involving them in nearby implementation plans.
- **Waste heat energy:** one very interesting additional dataset is excess heat energy generated by specific buildings (server farms, industrial sites, etc.). If not used directly, this heat energy can be distributed directly or stored for later usage. Using this data later within the map would largely increase its potential.
- **Solar energy:** The same applies to a data set containing geo references usage of solar energy (installations of photovoltaic modules/plants), to add it as an energy source. Reliable data is not comprehensive to this point but the potential is large
- **Economic data, cost calculations:** calculating the project costs for implementation relies on a very large number of factors. Creating a calculation model that draws from the information in the backend, could give the user a rough idea on the implementation costs. More research has to be done in order for those calculations to be somewhat reliable

Technical description

To understand the technical building blocks, it is important to stress the separation between front-end and back-end of the application.

The Back-end

The back-end service architecture is developed by the partner MCS Datalabs and consists of three main elements.

- **Geo-Database:** a database that stores and provides data with a focus on efficient management of information based on geolocations.
- **Input/Matching Database:** a data processing unit that obtains and processes incoming data and pre-processes requested data, including the joining of the data from three different sources (see the graphic below), before it is provided via the API.
- **The API:** the API provides several endpoints to interact with the features of the back-end service.

The Back-end-Features: in general, the back-end service provides two main features:

- The first feature is to obtain data sets from different sources, extract and process the relevant information and store them in a database.
- The second feature enables geolocation-oriented requests to access the stored and processed data.

Data Flow – Waste Water Heat Radar

FIGURE 19: DATA FLOW - WASTE WATER HEAT RADAR FOR WEB-APP AND ODD

The Front-end

The front-end service of the web application is developed by the partner Fraunhofer FOKUS and consists of the two main elements WWHR and ODD, which were described above.

The interactive map application (already presented under the name Waste-Water-Heat-Radar), allows user-oriented and location-oriented visualization of information. This information is requested from the API of the back-end service.

The integrated dashboard based on the Open Data Dashboard (ODD) depicts the second element and visualizes key figures for the present use case. The focus of the dashboard is to visualize important and general operating numbers as an overview about the progress and potentials.

Testing

The fully functional prototype has run through several internal tests, constant feedback, bug fixes, and improvements. Screenshots and demos of the prototype were shown within the entire REFLOW consortium, which gave additional feedback and helped to further improve the prototype. Screenshots and demos were also shown to potential users and important stakeholders at conferences to get feedback and to get a better understanding of their views.

Due to data privacy issues, the accurate potential dataset cannot be presented publicly and to external partners and stakeholders. This means that external testing of the full functionality of the application and all its features was not permitted as of now. The newly designed, randomized dataset however makes external testing possible. This paves the way for further rounds of feedback in workshops and when talking to specific groups of stakeholders in the following weeks.

After many iterations of development and constant internal testing, the experience of showing screenshots, demos and videos was very positive. The web application gained high interest at conferences and when talking to relevant stakeholders. The understanding of the usage of the WWHR has been described as very good by both stakeholders at conferences and relevant partners. Additionally, interest to further develop the application by adding other data sets (from Germany biggest energy supplier) has been expressed and discussions are ongoing.

Resources

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

The code of the prototype is available at:

<https://github.com/reflow-project/Berlin-pilot>

Due to data security concerns of BWB the application is not yet publicly available. The prototype is available with a randomized data set and can be accessed here:

<https://reflow-berlin.fokus.fraunhofer.de/map>

The app can be used via a web browser. No additional software is required. The map works with all common web browsers. The user accesses the web application through a website. Users will not need permission to use the application, although the application will not run with real data publicly. In the future, the map is planned to be open to the public with an accurate heat potential data set.

5.3 Cluj-Napoca pilot

5.3.1 Retrofit kit prototype

In the process of mitigating the consumption of energy in general, but also in the context of embracing circular economy principles, the municipality of Cluj-Napoca has an active approach of investment in increasing energy efficiency of public but also private buildings (especially large building blocks of condominiums). Local, national and European funds are used in these initiatives.

Of course, funding is limited and cannot cover all large-scale investments needed in order to have all public (and private) buildings in the city fully refurbished to substantially increase their energy efficiency coefficient. A first step could be a relatively minor retrofitting intervention, which would be both affordable and non-invasive (no major operations needed). Following this direction, the concept of a Retrofit Kit emerged from co-design meetings held with local stakeholders. This solution is versatile and could be easily replicated in different buildings depending on their size and purpose. Its versatility comes from the fact that it is basically a collection of different hardware devices with the relative operating software to make it fully functional.

During the co-design process, the Cluj-Napoca pilot had input from their colleagues inside the municipality that are in charge of public lighting and energy consumption. They indicated that the best solution for a testing pilot site would be the dormitory building at the “Energetic” Highschool campus. For that building, a customised number of hardware devices was acquired, and a smart metering system was put in place.

The technical specifications of the Retrofit Kit the Cluj-Napoca pilot deployed are:

- 145 LED lighting fixtures, used to replace the old lighting fixtures and provide better quality of lighting and also greatly increased energy efficiency
- 40 motion sensors to be used in powering up the lighting fixtures in the common areas (hallways, public toilets, etc). Also increases energy efficiency by having the lights turned off when nobody is around.
- One general panel and 5 smaller electrical panels, needed for better stability of the electrical system, and a necessary update for 2021 (the original panels were from the 1970s).

- 16 smart sockets, used to manage consumption for frequently used electronic devices (office computers, servers, refrigerators, washers, driers, etc). They are connected through a proprietary app that gives the admin control over the electricity that is consumed via these sockets
- 9 gateways, used to gather data from the smart sockets and other data transfers between different parts of the Retrofit Kit
- A smart metering system, which consists of digital electricity meters, each with a wireless communicator that sends consumption data to a centralized system, which integrates the data and stores it
- A bridge component that periodically sends the measured data to the Open Data Dashboard (the ODD is described in D2.4).

The last component has been specifically designed and implemented to connect the Retrofit Kit software system to the Open Data Dashboard, and its functionality consists of periodically calling the ODD API to upload the latest measurements. The ODD in this pilot has the role of presenting the general public with open data about energy consumption. Its application in the context of the Cluj pilot is shown in the following screenshot:

FIGURE 20: ODD DASHBOARD FOR CLUJ-NAPOCA USE CASE⁹

In the top part of the figure last year's energy consumption (2021) after the Retrofit Kit installation is compared to 2019. The consumption is generally lower except for August, due to the fact that August 2019 was a holiday month, while in 2021 schools were still partially running to make up for lessons missed because of the

⁹ Current version, latest version online at <https://reflow-dashboard.fokus.fraunhofer.de/superset/dashboard/25/>

pandemic. For the same reason the comparison is with 2019 and not with 2020, as in the latter school lessons were disrupted due to the pandemic (for a more detailed analysis see the upcoming D3.3).

The app described in the following section complements this by adding functionality that is specific to building owners/administrators.

5.3.2 Monitoring app

The smart metering system is also linked to a monitoring app, which allows building administrators to follow consumption in (almost) real time, with a data refresh cycle of 5 minutes.

The web app is available at <https://customers.rf-meters.com/reflow>. Screenshots of the app are shown below.

FIGURE 21: SCREENSHOT OF THE MONITORING APP

The app works as a dashboard with closed access, providing consumption, geo data and different visualizations on registered data.

FIGURE 22: SCREENSHOT OF THE MONITORING APP

Seven different devices register consumption in different areas of the building: i.e., laundry room, offices, bedroom floors etc. This offers greater granularity than data provided by the electricity company, which only has 2 metering devices for the entire campus.

FIGURE 23: SCREENSHOT OF THE MONITORING APP

The dashboard presents an overview of the consumption measured by each device in a specified time range.

FIGURE 24: SCREENSHOT OF THE MONITORING APP

The user can also zoom into a particular device to analyse the consumption patterns at different times of the day.

This way, the pilot intervention not only works in the direction of increasing energy efficiency, which is a fairly obvious scenario after installing more energy efficient equipment, but also in the direction of awareness. The user can be aware of how much energy is consumed, and most importantly, about their consumption behaviour. For example, it shows which part of the building and/or which function of the building is more energy intensive, what consumption patterns (hours, days) are normal and which ones are not, and what this user can do to become more energy efficient and adopt circular economy energy options. This last function of the dashboard works as a recommender and is designed at a basic level at the moment with a plan to be further developed and detailed as the retrofitting solution is further developed and made more modular. For now, the recommender is working on a set of 3 scenarios and generates a 3-step message for each scenario. This 3-step message consists of Analyse – Plan – Act sentences where Analyse comprises the identification of the cause, Plan the identification of Options and Act concrete actions. Scenario 1 includes the identification/alert when the consumption of a certain point is constantly increasing (10% or more) over the period of 3 months. Scenario 2 includes the identification/alert when the consumption of a point suddenly increases (20% or more from one day to another). Scenario 3 identifies increases/ high consumption in unjustified time periods (dormitory during the day for example or cafeteria overnight).

The Cluj-Napoca pilot sees the app as a tool both for consumption forecasting and budgeting for the future, but also for prioritising future investments in energy efficiency (i.e., if the laundry room consumes excessive amounts of energy, it is paramount that the washing and drying machines be updated. A more efficient washing machine could have a major impact on consumption for the whole building.)

The Retrofit Kit's technical specifications for the pilot site (the dormitory building inside the Energetic High School campus) have been identified with the help of the local stakeholders, as a result of the co-design meetings the Cluj-Napoca pilot held with them. These technical specifications have been used to compile the tender books for the acquisition process and are therefore publicly available (see Appendix).

The Retrofit Kit hardware and software are proprietary since they are developed by a company external to Reflow, RF Meters. The code of the bridge component is proprietary to RF Meters and was not developed specifically within Reflow, but it was included in the overall concept of the Retrofit Kit.

5.4 Milan pilot

5.4.1 Milano PrimaSeconda prototype

In the context of the food value circulating in the city of Milan, there are some very promising initiatives that are tackling the re-distribution of excess food (as described in the next section "Foody Zero Waste"), while other initiatives focus on the regeneration of flows of edible resources through circular economy loops.

In the food sector, some food materials are processed into "circular economy" products, such as products to feed animals or to create other industrial food products. When the logistics chain ends, the goods, due to the intrinsic properties of fresh food, are close to the moment of perishability. Therefore, innovations that generate a more connected and intelligent integration of services, such as the optimization of flows and introducing new last mile retail services, for example a smart locker or delivery services (as described in the section "Food Market 4.0") is needed in the logistics sector.

On the other hand, there are also initiatives focused on up-cycling food material flows such as Ibrida Birra¹⁰ and FungoBox¹¹. These entities act as the transformer of a material (for Ibrida breadcrumbs, for FungoBox coffee waste). In this way, they close a loop, in circular economy terms, adding value to "discarded" assets by turning them into new products.

Ibrida Birra is an organisation that produces locally branded beer made from unsold bread through partnerships with a network of neighbourhood bakeries and with a local brewery in Milan. The branded beer is then sold in the neighbourhood. This is the context of the PrimaSeconda scenario, in which tools developed in Reflow's WP2 are used to create a customized web application (PrimaSeconda for Ibrida Birra) to manage the steps of the process and to facilitate the job for the "orchestrator" of the process (i.e. Ibrida Birra).

¹⁰ <https://ibridabirra.com/it/home>

¹¹ <https://www.fungobox.it/>

Up-cycled products (such as in this case, bread) have similar characteristics: the collection of food waste is very decentralized and therefore expensive, it is very hard to have standardized quality, and the paperwork can be cumbersome. PrimaSeconda aims at piloting a tool, supported by the features of WP2 tools, that is configurable and that can manage or orchestrate this kind of circular economy loops.

Concretely, PrimaSeconda is a web application that supports the processing of recurring food surpluses and increases value creation with a transformation process (in this case, a brewery).

The goal is to give value to the use of food surplus and its transformation through:

- traceability and monitoring of circular processes;
- measurement of products and resources in circular productions;
- empowerment of community agents and promotion of circular goods

The solution supports organizations (SMEs, start-ups, NGOs) that claim to have a closed circular loop but do not have technical tools to track/trace or prove that. PrimaSeconda monitors material flows, therefore it can certify that particular processes are circular and it can "quantify" the circular loops, thereby showing their value.

The web app lets the organization manage the process of transformation. The flow of the circular value chain needs to be modelled beforehand through a high-level description diagram, using Miro or other flow chart tools.

FIGURE 25: VALUE FLOWS DIAGRAM OF THE IBRIDA BIRRA USE CASE¹².

The pilot case can be summarised in these steps (in brackets the Ibrida Birra case):

- Engagement and Organizing (involve bakeries to collect and donate unsold bread)
- Planning the production batch (ask for the amount of bread needed for the batch)
- Collecting (when the right amount of unsold bread is ready to be collected)

¹² A high-res version of this figure is at: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/blob/main/MilanoPrimaSeconda/fig/Frame%201.jpg>

- Sorting (quality check of the bread)
- Transforming (grinding the breadcrumbs and the brewery process)
- Distributing (to the bakeries that donated the unsold bread and collaborative agents)
- Selling (communicating the branded beer, organize event to maximize the value of the circular product)

The agents are (see figure below):

- Circular Material Producer (for example bakeries)
- Transformer agent (for example breweries)
- Circular Flow Orchestrator & Circular Loop Product Owner (Ibrida Birra).

FIGURE 26: THE AGENTS IN THE IBRIDA BIRRA USE CASE

In more general terms the production of a regenerated product can be described as follow:

- Circular Value Creation (made by Circular Flow Orchestrator & Circular Loop Product Owner)
 - Value Flows design (ideation, research, test, economic assessment)
 - Circular Value Creation and Proposition (branding, marketing, channels, customers)
- Circular Resources & Agents operations
 - Circular Material Flows (design the subprocesses and the inputs/outputs of material and data)
 - Circular Material Producers (find and manage the producer of a secondary raw material)
 - Circular Material Transformers (production deals with agents transform, i.e. brewery)
 - Circular Selling Channel (find and manage commercial deals with local retails)
- Product Resources
 - Label and branding assets
 - Specification of the material collected and regenerated
 - Recipe and/or designs of the product

The web app serves the needs of the Flow Orchestrator during Flow Operation. With this app, a user can:

- trigger the new production of a batch (in this case, Ibrida Beer decides to produce a batch of beer)
- input resources collected from the Producers
- Update the status of the production chain through the various sub-processes (to be collected, collected, sorted, prepared for transformations, transformed, packaged (bottle, beer keg, etc.), distributed, or sold

The web app is an operation user interface that works utilizing the REFLOW OS API.

The Value Flows model is specified using GraphQL based on a detailed REA model, which has been described at a higher level with graphics tools (as discussed above).

Through the app, the users can update the status of the various resources in the value chain.

When a production process is finished, the user can analyse the collected data (i.e., how many kg of resources are collected, how many of them are discarded, how many are effectively up-cycled in a “reflow”). In this way, the production batch steps can create a system that creates accountability for the initiatives (i.e., by demonstrating that in a certain period a certain amount of circular resources are produced) and can serve as a tracing system for customers who wants to verify the provenance of the product.

PrimaSeconda makes APIs calls to REFLOW OS with the following data (see Figure 27 below):

- circular material producer
- bread collected
- bread usable
- Date
- Note

The screenshot shows a web interface for a 'Material input form'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Input', 'Summary', and a menu icon. The form itself is titled 'Material input form' and contains several input fields: 'Production Batch' with a dropdown menu showing '22Feb02', 'From' with a dropdown menu showing 'Varisco Bakery', 'Collected [kg]' with a numeric input field showing '4', 'Usable [kg]' with a numeric input field showing '3', 'Date & Time' with a date and time input field showing '2022-01-16 10:22', and 'Notes' with a large text area. At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: 'Reset' and 'Submit'.

FIGURE 27

REFLOW OS stores these data and returns two main outputs to PrimaSeconda:

- Flow data summary about resources used for transformed products
- Material passport with traceability of circular products

Technical building blocks

Technical building blocks are made with Node-RED (already introduced in section “Graphic-based flow simulation tool”), a programming tool for wiring together hardware devices, APIs, and online services. Node-RED provides a browser-based editor that makes it easy to wire together flows, using the wide range of nodes in the palette that can be deployed to its runtime in a single click.

After the first prototype iterations, other open-source tools were used to create a simpler and richer user interface. Such tools are called low-code tools and are used as internal tools or for business app creation. There are many possibilities but, in our scope, we chose the platforms that had open-source licensing. The one WeMake used during the pilot prototyping phase is called AppSmith¹³.

AppSmith can be programmed to be a custom touchpoint for the user and the process through User Interface elements that act using the REFLOW OS API through GraphQL calls.

These kinds of tools are relatively easy to use and to deploy, fact that is especially important because the app’s Business Logic needs to perfectly fit the operation steps. These features are very important considering that organizations in this field are not structurally equipped to have neither an SAP ERP system nor many resources to spend on digital twins' platforms or tools.

¹³ <https://www.appsmith.com/>

The PrimaSeconda web app for Ibrida Birra was developed following co-design and co-creation principles and methodology. The testing of the app was done in virtual meetings since the production of Ibrida Beer was not done in the timeframe of the development and prototyping. The next production is being planned for June 2022 and testing in the field has been planned.

Repository: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/tree/main/MilanoPrimaSeconda>

5.4.2 Milano Foody Zero Waste Prototype (BOTTO)

After 6 months of field research and co-design activities conducted with the stakeholders engaged in the Foody Zero Waste scenario of the Milan Pilot, it became clear that there was a need to support the donation of surplus fruits and vegetables within the wholesale market of Milan (Foody - So.Ge.M.I.).

The stakeholders engaged in the Foody Zero Waste scenario are the following:

- **So.Ge.M.I - Foody:** So.Ge.M.I is the corporation that runs the city's four wholesale agricultural and food markets - for fruit and vegetables, fish, meat and flowers - on behalf of the municipality of Milan, supporting and managing their spaces, internal logistics and services to suppliers and to the public. Foody is the name of the fruit and vegetable wholesale market.
- **So.Ge.M.I wholesalers:** Companies operating within the Foody market, that are involved in the project as donors of surplus food production. They also include local producers.
 - Stakeholders involved in the co-design phase:
 - Frutteto Casagrande Srl
 - Gala Fruit Srl
 - Orticoltori Milanesi
 - Stakeholders involved in the testing phase:
 - Babaco Market
 - Frutteto Casagrande Srl
 - Gala Fruit Srl
 - Ortofrutticola Milanese Srl
- **RECUP:** Association acting as intermediary for the donation of surplus fruit and vegetables.
- **Italian Red Cross:** NGO collecting and giving out surplus food to those in need.
 - Entities involved in the co-design phase:
 - Italian Red Cross – Opera
 - Entities involved in the testing phase:
 - Italian Red Cross – Opera
 - Italian Red Cross - San Donato
- **OpenDot:** Fablab coordinating the prototype and testing phase

Currently, both the identification of surplus production that could be saved, considering also food safety, and the communication with NGOs dealing with its redistribution to people in need, are time consuming. The logistics process is very complex and is not able to actually track and trace the quantity of surplus production.

Food donation also means much paperwork for each actor involved, without necessarily obtaining any incentives in return.

Thanks to various participatory sessions, OpenDot designed and developed BOTTO, a solution capable of enabling a virtuous process, a product-service that facilitates the communication between wholesalers, the association RECUP and the Italian Red Cross, and that monitors and tracks the quantity of surplus food generated, saved and wasted.

What does the prototype do?

Botto is a product and a service that facilitates the communication between wholesalers, the association RECUP, and the Italian Red Cross. BOTTO also allows to digitize flows, monitor the movement of goods, generate relevant documentation and keep track of data that is useful for all the stakeholders.

BOTTO's goals are to:

- simplify the communication between the actors involved in the donation process;
- reduce the amount of paperwork by digitalizing important information (i.e., transaction receipts);
- track and trace the material flow including location, date, time, wholesaler ID, packages quantity, state of product, weight (in kg), type of product.

The use case and its material flow has been modelled in Value Flows using the tool presented in section “Graphic modelling tool”. This is represented in the picture (FIGURE 28) below.

FIGURE 28

How does a user use it?

BOTTO is composed of an IoT device and a Telegram Bot. The IoT device is used only by the wholesalers, while the Telegram Bot is available for both RECUP and The Italian Red Cross.

Through the IoT device, wholesalers send RECUP a notification, which relays the quantity of surplus and the reason behind this surplus (i.e., ripening level, packaging problems etc.), simply by pressing and rotating two buttons.

At this stage, the quantities are measured in “packages”.

FIGURE 29: INTERACTION WITH THE IOT DEVICE - THE USER INTERACTS WITH THE MENU USING THE 2 BUTTONS, ACTIONS ARE SUPPORTED BY SOUND AND LIGHT.

FIGURE 30: INTERNAL COMPONENTS OF THE IOT DEVICE

The notification sent by the IoT device goes through REFLOW OS and is monitored by a Telegram Bot, which reports new donations and facilitates the redistribution process through dedicated Telegram Channels (“BOTTO IN” and “BOTTO OUT”).

FIGURE 31: INTERACTION BETWEEN THE IOT DEVICE AND THE TELEGRAM CHANNELS

“BOTTO IN” is used by RECUP, while “BOTTO OUT” is available for both RECUP and the Italian Red Cross.

RECUP uses the Telegram Channels “BOTTO IN” and “BOTTO OUT” for:

- “BOTTO IN” - Accepting or refusing the donation received from the wholesalers;

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

- “BOTTO IN” - Confirming the quantity that has been donated;
- “BOTTO IN” - Registering the type of product that has been donated (i.e., apples), its original weight in Kilos and the remaining weight after the selection process (for example, donated products with mould need to be discarded);
- “BOTTO IN” and “BOTTO OUT” - Redistributing the selected product to the Italian Red Cross, stating the weight and the type of product that is available;
- “BOTTO IN” - Registering the collection of the product that has been redistributed and collected by the Italian Red Cross.

The Italian Red Cross uses the Telegram Channel “BOTTO OUT” to be notified of the available products from RECUP and to inform RECUP if they are interested in it or not.

This process is represented in the picture below, focussing first on the steps and then on the data exchanged at each step:

FIGURE 32

FIGURE 33

By interacting directly with the Bot, the Italian Red Cross can also obtain a receipt which lists all the products they have collected from RECUP in a PDF format and that can be easily shared by email.

Data: gio 10 febbraio 2022

<p>RECUP APS Via Urbano III, 3 20123, Milano (MI) CF: 97759920156 ortomercato.recup@gmail.com</p>	<p>Croce Rossa Italiana Comitato Dell'Area Sud Milanese Via Giovanni Marcora 2 20090, Opera (MI) PI/CF: 08486730966 SDI: 3ZJY534 areasudmilanese@cri.it cl.areasudmilanese@cert.cri.it 02 5760 2152</p>
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Trasferimento beni a titolo gratuito

Descrizione merce ritirata	Quantità
Cavolo Romano	221 kg
Meloni	20 kg
Spinaci	13 kg

Il presente documento non ha rilevanza fiscale in quanto il trasporto è effettuato nell'ambito dell'attività istituzionale dell'Ente, che non ha fini di lucro e non svolge attività commerciale.

Data: mar 22 febbraio 2022

<p>RECUP APS Via Urbano III, 3 20123, Milano (MI) CF: 97759920156 ortomercato.recup@gmail.com</p>	<p>Croce Rossa Italiana Comitato di San Donato Milanese OdV Via Croce Rossa 6 20097, San Donato Milanese (MI) PI/CF: 08468890960 SDI: KRRH6B9 sandonatomilanese@cri.it cl.sandonatomilanese@cert.cri.it 02 5272 137</p>
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Trasferimento beni a titolo gratuito

Descrizione merce ritirata	Quantità
Ravanelli	15 kg
Banane	40 kg

Il presente documento non ha rilevanza fiscale in quanto il trasporto è effettuato nell'ambito dell'attività istituzionale dell'Ente, che non ha fini di lucro e non svolge attività commerciale.

FIGURE 34: TWO RECEIPTS GENERATED BY BOTTO FOR THE TWO ITALIAN RED CROSS ENTITIES

The data collected by BOTTO are available in three different dashboards, one for each stakeholder, namely RECUP, wholesalers and the Italian Red Cross. Below is a visualisation of the RECUP dashboard (the other two dashboards are similar).

FIGURE 35: THE DASHBOARD SHOWS THE QUANTITY OF SURPLUS DONATED TO RECUP. THE WASTE GENERATED FROM IT (DISCARDED PRODUCTS AS PER NOT EDIBLE ONES) AND THE ACTUAL AMOUNT SAVED. THE PIE CHART SHOWS THE REASON BEHIND THE DONATION.

Technical building blocks

BOTTO is made of 3 main components:

REFLOW OS: An instance of REFLOW OS back-end, deployed locally via a Docker container on our own server. The IoT device and the Telegram Bot send and receive data to and from it.

Botto IoT device: The device is based on ESP-32-S2 microcontrollers with the firmware coded in C++. The microcontroller communicates via GraphQL over HTTPS using a Wi-Fi network to the REFLOW OS back-end, both for sending notifications about available surplus and for obtaining updates on their acceptance status from RECUP.

Several Botto IoT devices have been built and distributed to the project stakeholders (i.e., the wholesalers involved in the test phase, except for Babaco Market).

The following scheme maps the interaction of the Botto IoT electronic device and defines the user inputs, the resulting outputs and the feedbacks from and to the network. The scheme represents the different states the device can be in, and what inputs or events cause the device to transition to a new state.

FIGURE 36

More technical details about the IoT device are reported in the Appendix.

Botto Telegram bot: A suite of Telegram Bots has been developed in the Node.js¹⁴ JavaScript runtime. These bots update users about the events described above and let them interact with the system. The bots are deployed on the same server where REFLOW OS is running.

The model used by the bot is according to the Value Flows vocabulary, and defines 3 different entities: agents (*providers* and *receivers*), the resource units (named *colli* and *kilograms*) and a category, named *sorted*, to mark the sorted economic resources. A configuration file maps the bot's internal ids with the ids in REFLOW OS of the corresponding entities.

The bot implements a polling mechanism to periodically perform a check if new donations are available for RECUP. The polling time can be adjusted following the user's preferences. A handling mechanism of the new offers has been implemented which automatically refuses a new offer in case RECUP does not provide an explicit answer within a specified time range (default: 30 minutes), while providing a reminder to RECUP before the timeout is reached. The reminder timeout, which is configurable, is set by default to 5 minutes.

All the interactions mentioned earlier that can be performed by RECUP and Red Cross with the bot are implemented via specific GraphQL queries and mutations, described more in detail in the next section.

How are Reflow tools used?

REFLOW OS works in this use case as a single back-end for the whole **data input** process. The IoT device, as mentioned earlier, directly connects to REFLOW OS via specific GraphQL calls in order to perform three main actions: login, offer creation and offer status check.

In particular, it performs the login and stores the obtained credentials for each agent who owns a BOTTO device, namely wholesalers and local producers.

When requested by the user, through the steps described above, the physical device sends a new offer (called *intent* in Value Flows), specifying the available quantity in terms of packages (with the `hasNumericalValue` field) and a textual description of the reason of donation (with the `note` field).

After having registered the offer as an intent, the bot saves the newly created intent `id` in a temporary array (`offerIds`) and adopting a polling mechanism it starts checking periodically whether an offer has been accepted.

Also for the BOTTO Telegram Bot, the REFLOW OS back-end represents the only endpoint towards which the various operations are executed via GraphQL queries and mutations. The main adopted mutations are: `login`, `updateIntent`, `createEconomicEvent`, `createOffer`, `createCommitment` and `createSatisfaction`, while the main queries are related to the same entities, in particular: `intentsPages`,

¹⁴ <https://nodejs.org/en/>

intent, intents, economicResourcesFiltered, satisfactions and satisfaction¹⁵.

The **Open Data Dashboard** shows the collected data and represents the main interface for the **data output** process.

As mentioned above, we have developed three different dashboards, one for each stakeholder (RECUP, wholesalers and the Italian Red Cross). These dashboards, designed together with FOKUS, show the data collected between 2022-02-10 and 2022-02-25 and are accessible at:

Wholesaler: <https://reflow-dashboard.fokus.fraunhofer.de/superset/dashboard/24/>

RECUP: <https://reflow-dashboard.fokus.fraunhofer.de/superset/dashboard/21/>

Red Cross: <https://reflow-dashboard.fokus.fraunhofer.de/superset/dashboard/23/>

The data is updated once a day and shows the quantity of food donated, the number of kilos saved and wasted, and the reason behind each donation (RECUP dashboard only).

Testing the prototype

Botto has been tested in a real environment during a 3-week period, from the 10th until the 25th of February. The testing phase lasted shorter than originally planned, due to some technical difficulties related to the availability of some components of the IoT device, as well as some limitations of its functionalities which delayed the deployment.

The three wholesalers chosen for the testing phase (Casagrande srl, Gala Fruit srl and Ortofrutticola Milanese) were selected by SO.GE.M.I. and RECUP, considering a) the volumes of products they handle and b) their technology readiness in order to get a broad range of input/subjects.

We requested these wholesalers to keep track of their surplus products everyday by using the IoT device even if RECUP was active in the market only on Thursdays. By doing so, we wanted to see the weekly amount of surpluses on the wholesalers' side, and the potentiality of RECUP's intervention, if they would collect and sort the products every day of the week.

The testing phase began with the installation of the IoT device in each wholesalers' stand (Casagrande srl, Gala Fruit srl and Ortofrutticola Milanese), and with one-to-one tutorials on how to use it. The instructions were also given to "BOTTO IN" and "BOTTO OUT" Telegram channels (RECUP, Italian Red Cross San Donato and Italian Red Cross Opera), and all their members were added to the channels, so that they could interact with the Bot and see all of the notifications.

OpenDot supported RECUP and the wholesalers during the whole duration of the test phase, participating in their activities within Foody.

¹⁵ For more details on performed queries refer to <https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/blob/main/Foody%20Zero%20Waste/telegram-bot/queries.js>.

At the end of the testing phase a total of 9577,20 kg were donated, 875 kg went to waste, with a total of 8701 kg were given to people in need.

These numbers also include the surplus production given by other wholesalers within Foody, who were not included in the test phase and who didn't have the IoT device; RECUP was able to track this surplus thanks to the Telegram Bot.

In terms of numbers, the winter season is known to have a lower amount of donations compared to the summer season. This is because wholesalers can preserve food for longer periods during the winter season and prefer to try to sell it, even at a lower price, before donating it.

BOTTO (both the IoT device and the Telegram Bot) received positive feedback, especially regarding its ease of use. The test phase helped identify not only a series of adjustments to be made on the technical side, but also some organisational inconsistencies on the stakeholders' side.

As a matter of fact, adding technology to a process requires clear steps and operations that should be homogeneously executed by RECUP's team members. In this case, the test highlighted the importance of each RECUP's volunteers, and the necessity to define clear roles between them.

Through the test, we also noticed that there is a need for a homogeneous database of the fruit and vegetables available from the wholesale market. At the moment RECUP inserts names of products without following a specific list which introduces duplicate names for the same product.

From a technical point of view, the first day of testing already enabled us to review some of the steps of the Telegram Bot, both in "BOTTO IN" and "BOTTO OUT", in order to simplify the process for RECUP and the Italian Red Cross. In fact, the two entities of the Italian Red Cross (San Donato and Opera) that took part in the test had different needs, as they dealt with different volumes of donation and therefore couldn't collect the same amount of surplus.

Unfortunately, due to some technical issues with the REFLOW OS back-end, it wasn't possible to transfer the same EconomicResources to more than one receiver¹⁶. Consequently, we could not generate specific receipts to each Red Cross entity that, most of the time, received different quantities of the same resource. This problem has affected the entire test phase of the project.

Despite the reduced period of time, interesting observations emerged from the testing phase, and the data and feedback collected were very useful. BOTTO showed great potential in tracking data and simplifying communication between the actors involved, but it also showed how much more can be done from a software and hardware point of view, in order to better satisfy the actors' needs and to create an even better and more intuitive flow. In the future we will investigate the possibility of expanding the software and hardware functionality, as part of our exploitation plans, with the aim to engage with actors from different fields (for example fashion, constructions, other type of food) who are interested in improving their donations activities.

Resources

¹⁶ As documented in <https://github.com/dyne/reflow-os/issues/31>

The code is hosted on the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/tree/main/Foody%20Zero%20Waste>

In particular the code of the IoT device's components, along with other technical information as well as some documentation of the prototype, can be found here:

<https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/tree/main/Foody%20Zero%20Waste/physical-device>

The source code and installation instructions of Telegram bot can be found here:

<https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/tree/main/Foody%20Zero%20Waste/telegram-bot>

Trying the prototype

Our REFLOW OS instance is publicly accessible over the internet at <http://93.47.79.216:4000/>.

The Telegram bots need individual approval for new users to be included and become operative. The IoT device needs to be specifically produced and installed for new users, but the generic code is published at the above-mentioned links.

Here is a list of requirements for each component, in order to be able to use BOTTO:

REFLOW OS: a publicly addressed server capable of running Docker;

Telegram Bot: a publicly addressed server capable of running Node.Js

IoT device: the physical device (or a compatible setup) is necessary, and to operate it requires internet over a wi-fi network and user credentials for the REFLOW OS instance.

5.4.3 Food Market 4.0

Description of functionality

In recent years, municipal markets in many cities have been the subject of revitalisation and regeneration actions aimed at promoting projects and initiatives concerning the sustainability and circularity of urban agri-food systems. The City of Milan is starting to consider the municipal food markets as actors that can stimulate the transition towards circular business models, by adopting sustainable processes of access, consumption and use of products and services linked to the agri-food system.

The policy of the Municipality of Milan foresees the reorganisation of the system of covered markets which includes two basic elements:

- a new management model for the markets which favours their restoration/infrastructural upgrade and revitalisation, considering sustainability and circularity as relevant aspects;
- a more integrated and sustainable relationship between the general market (So.Ge.Mi) and the network of covered markets.

The field research carried out in the Milan pilot showed that at present:

- local markets do not have an adequate level of digitalisation (lack of digital infrastructure, traders with inadequate digital skills, etc.) that would enable them to manage and monitor food flows;
- there is no integrated system for tracking food (especially fruits and vegetables) from the general market to covered markets.

The *Food Market 4.0 Dashboard* is an integrated system of both hardware and software solutions for municipal markets which aim to prevent food waste. The Food Market 4.0 Dashboard includes inventory tracking, logistics planning, and controlling for the inbound and outbound fruits and vegetables flowing through municipal markets.

Additionally, Food Market 4.0 Dashboard also provides physical touchpoints such as a smart scale and reusable boxes with integrated RFID. The system works to standardize the process of tracing and monitoring food flows enabling the covered market vendors.

The general vision and concept of Food Market 4.0 Dashboard includes all actors participating in the management of fruit and vegetable flows: farmers, wholesalers, vendors, deliverers, technology and logistics providers. Through the gathered data, all the actors involved can optimise their actions, resulting in an overall waste reduction.

The actors involved in the co-design, prototyping and testing of Food Market 4.0 Dashboard are:

- the general market So.Ge.Mi., who is interested in understanding the functioning of the tracking and monitoring of fruit and vegetable flows towards covered markets (So.Ge.Mi. is implementing a new food hub model called Foody, a fruit and vegetable wholesale market also discussed in the previous chapters).
- the municipal covered market of Morsenchio and the consortium that manages it, who hosts the experimentation of the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard system;
- the Mazzucchi Ortofrutta shop, who experiments with the functioning of the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard system;
- the Politecnico di Milano (also called Polimi), who conceived, developed and modelled the whole design and prototyping process of the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard system;
- the Municipality of Milan, who is interested in the development of innovation initiatives that are part of the Food Policy;
- CPR System, a company specialised in providing services for circularity in agri-food distribution systems, who has voluntarily collaborated in the experimentation of the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard system.

The vision is to replicate the same approach to other markets and other vendors based on the lessons learnt in the present scenario.

The prototype Food Market 4.0 system consists of the following elements:

- *smart boxes* for fruit and vegetables (also called CPR boxes from the above-mentioned company that produces them), fully recyclable, foldable and equipped with RFID tags;
- *smart scale*, a system composed of a weighing bench, to which is connected a webcam (to recognise the goods), an RFID reader, a thermal printer (for fiscal receipts), and a Mini PC with a touch display to visualise the operations;
- *smart gate*, consisting of RFID antennas that can be positioned within the market in the stall, in the warehouse and on the vehicles that transport the fruit and vegetables;

- a digital dashboard that allows data monitoring on the flow of goods and the generation of data in formats compatible with tools such as the Open Data Dashboard.

The Food Market 4.0 prototype was designed to be compatible with tools and devices commonly available on the market and used by fruit and vegetable retailers (e.g., digital scales), but also to be implemented using open-source technology. The Politecnico team designed a smart scale OS and a gate OS system that allows the positioning of RFID antennas in various environments, together with the possibility to monitor the conditions of the stored or transported food.

The Food Market 4.0 Dashboard includes the following functionality:

- **Hardware** - Handling of goods through an efficient hardware system that avoids damaging the products. The Food Market 4.0 Dashboard also provides markets with RFID integrated boxes which are reusable, standardised and are compatible in size with an installed smart scale. This facilitates the process of tracking and tracing and reduces packaging.
- **Check-In** – Recognition and tracking of incoming and outgoing products through digitised checkpoints and tags applied to the reusable and standardised boxes.
- **Virtual Organisation** – Management of exhibited and stored goods through an interactive Dashboard where the collected data is displayed, which enables the user to make decisions based on data.
- **Redistribution** – Opens opportunities to further distribute fruits and vegetables to local corporations like local food delivery services or local NGOs or charities. The dashboard also enables the user to identify the number of surplus fruits and vegetables.

Food Market 4.0 Dashboard has implemented and modelled the following Value flows, including front-end and back-end operations:

FIGURE 37: THE GENERAL OVERVIEW OF VALUE FLOWS FOR FOOD MARKET 4.0 DASHBOARD¹⁷.

¹⁷ A high-res version of the figure is available at https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/blob/main/Food%20Market%204.0/fig/DASHBOARD%204.0_VALUEFLOWS%20-%20Frame%201.jpg

FIGURE 38: THE VALUE FLOWS FOR FOOD MARKET 4.0 DASHBOARD WITH ITS FRONT-END AND BACK-END¹⁸.

How does a user use it?

Once the products have been purchased in disposable boxes at the general market (SO.GE.MI.), they are unloaded at the municipal market and unboxed into the CPR boxes using the scale equipped with the RFID reader. This process associates a product to each CPR box and performs a check-in of the goods entering the market (see Figure 39 below).

¹⁸ A high-res version of the figure is available at: https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/blob/main/Food%20Market%204.0/fig/DASHBOARD%204.0_VALUEFLOWS%20-%20Frame%202.jpg

FIGURE 39: THIS BLUEPRINT (PART 1) SHOWS THE FIRST THREE CLUSTERS OF ACTIVITIES: 1) PURCHASE AND UNLOAD; 2) UNBOXING AND CHECK IN OF THE GOODS; 3) DISPLAY OF GOODS IN THE STALL.

The products contained in the CPR boxes can then be displayed in the stall or stored in the warehouse, which is equipped with antennas and an RFID reader to monitor the inbound and outbound products from the warehouse (see Figure 40 below).

FIGURE 40: THIS BLUEPRINT (PART 2) SHOWS THESE CLUSTERS OF ACTIVITIES: 4) CHECK-IN AND STORAGE; 5) WEIGHING AND SALES; 6) REFILL OF THE GOODS.

By weighing the products to be sold through the scale system provided, the dashboard will also allow to visualise and monitor the direct sales as well as sales through delivery and picking services. Finally, the dashboard includes the possibility to track the movement of products from an almost empty to a partially full box, in case of refilling (rightmost part of Figure 40 above).

Technical building blocks

The prototype of Food Market 4.0 Dashboard has been implemented in the following way (see figures below):

- configuration of existing hardware tools (reusable boxes, scale system, gate system);
- design and prototyping of the dashboard that connects all the hardware tools;
- design and prototyping the open-source version for the scale and gate systems.

THE REUSABLE BOX: THE BASIC ELEMENT OF THE SYSTEM

FIGURE 41: THE CPR SYSTEM REUSABLE CRATES

FIGURE 42: THE SCALE SYSTEM WITH A DIGITAL SCALE CONNECTED TO AN RFID READER, A MINI-PC, TOUCH DISPLAY AND THERMAL PRINTER.

FIGURE 43: THE GATE SYSTEM IS COMPOSED BY RFID ANTENNAS THAT CAN BE POSITIONED WITHIN THE STALL, THE WAREHOUSE AND ON THE MEANS OF TRANSPORTATION

FIGURE 44: THE DIGITAL DASHBOARD LANDING PAGE WHICH LEADS TO OPERATIONS RELATED TO PURCHASING, CHECKING-IN, SELLING, AND REFILLING.

FIGURE 45: THE RENDERED 3D MODEL OF THE OPEN-SOURCE SCALE SYSTEM

FIGURE 46: THE "MAKING OF" THE OPEN-SOURCE SCALE SYSTEM PROTOTYPE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

FIGURE 47: THE OPEN GATE UNIT AND EXTERNAL LAYOUT

FIGURE 48: THE OPEN GATE MAIN COMPONENTS (LEFT) AND THE OPEN DATE POSITIONING ON A TRUCK (RIGHT)

The information architecture of Food Market 4.0 Dashboard (Figure 49 below) is composed of:

- **Integrator:** connected to all modules to dispatch all messages between them;
- **Controller:** to control the flow of all processes of the system;
- **Data manager:** to collect data locally;
- **RFID antenna (BIG):** manages the reading procedure of RFID tagged boxes while moving between stall and storage, the antenna is positioned on the stall and on the storage room entrance;
- **RFID antenna (SMALL):** manages the reading procedure of RFID tagged boxes when weighed on the weighing scale;
- **Certified Scale:** module for reading and sending weight from a certified scale;
- **Open-Source Scale:** module for reading and sending weight from a certified scale;
- **Touch screen:** responsible to manage the interaction of the user with the touch screen;
- **Camera:** responsible to integrate the check-in/selling activity with visual recognition of the goods;
- **Thermal printer:** manages the printing actions sent to the thermal printer;
- **Smart labels:** connects to the smart label system to display information on smart labels;

INFORMATION ARCHITECTURE - REFLOW (POLIMI)

FIGURE 49: THE INFORMATION ARCHITECTURE OF FOOD MARKET 4.0 DASHBOARD ("REFLOW CLOUD REFERS TO ANY GENERIC SYSTEM DEVELOPED IN THE REFLOW PROJECT ABLE TO STORE DATA OF THE PURCHASING SESSIONS, E.G. OPEN DATA DASHBOARD, REFLOW OS).

How are Reflow tools used?

The Food Market 4.0 Dashboard used Open Data Dashboard (ODD) to experiment with data visualisation related to the monitoring of inbound and outbound products (fruits and vegetables) from the municipal covered market. During the test phase (lasting one week) the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard generated data on the flows of fruits and vegetables that were purchased at the SO.GE.MI. food hub by a greengrocer operating in the Morsenchio municipal market. During the test, sufficient data has been collected to develop a realistic simulation on the flows of fruits and vegetables purchased, stored, and sold by the greengrocer in one year.

The ODD offers two kinds of visualisations for the data collected by the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard:

1. Visualisations related to food tracking and monitoring:

- a. type and quantities of fruits and vegetables purchased, stored, and sold (daily, monthly, and yearly) by a typical operator of a municipal market. This visualisation allows to track the inbound and outbound fruit and vegetable from the municipal market;
 - b. type and amount of food waste calculated through the difference of fruits and vegetables purchased and sold within the municipal market;
 - c. general overview about the number of fruits and vegetables purchased and sold.
2. Visualisations related to prediction of food sales and food waste reduction/prevention:
- a. prevision of food waste calculated through the difference of fruits and vegetables purchased and sold within the municipal market;
 - b. calculation of the cost of goods transportation, to optimise the processes of purchasing and managing the flow of products to and from the market. This is possible by calculating a unit cost that includes the actual costs of purchasing and transporting products and the estimated costs of moving products to and from the point of sale and the costs associated with the sales process.

This first set of visualisations aims to provide an example of what could be visualised on a city-wide scale considering all municipal market operators (Milan has 23 municipal covered markets).

The Figure 50 below shows visualisations related to the first bullet point above:

FIGURE 50: ODD DASHBOARD FOR FOOD MARKET 4.0 - FOOD TRACKING AND MONITORING¹⁹

¹⁹ Current version, latest version online at <https://reflow-dashboard.fokus.fraunhofer.de/superset/dashboard/27/>

Testing

The prototype has been tested twice:

- A first set of internal tests conducted in the Lab Polifactory to set up the whole system and verify the functioning of all its components.
- A real test within the **Morsenchio Municipal Covered Market took place on a daily basis** (period: 27th January - 4th February 2022). All the hardware elements have been temporarily installed within the Market (see figures below). In particular, the scale system has been installed within the stall while the gate system has been installed both in the stall and in the warehouse. The CPR boxes provided to the market greengrocer have been utilised to test all the activities foreseen by the scenario (check-in, warehousing, sale, refill). In this way, it has been possible to measure data related to the quantity and type of fruit and vegetables entering and leaving the market, also calculating the amount of food discarded each day.

FIGURE 51: POLIMI TEAM WHILE INSTALLING THE PROTOTYPE WITHIN MORSENCHIO MARKET FRUIT AND VEGETABLE STALL

FIGURE 52: MR. MAZZUCCHI TRYING OUT THE FOOD MARKET 4.0 DASHBOARD CONNECTED TO THE SMART SCALE

The prototype has been tested by the market greengrocer (Mr. Paolo Mazzucchi) and his collaborators, supported by the POLIMI team.

Despite the lack of adequate digital skills to understand and use the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard system, Mr. Mazzucchi appreciated the benefits of using reusable boxes and the tracking functionality offered by the dashboard connected to the system.

The installation of the hardware elements of the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard system (e.g. RFID antennas) in the stall required no intervention in the shop and warehouse and no adaptation of the existing equipment.

While Mr. Mazzucchi acknowledged that the installation of the system was relatively simple, he pointed out that the new system, which is more complex than the existing one, will have an impact on both the positioning of his tools and equipment and the reorganisation of his workflow.

Resources

The digital dashboard software repository is available at <https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot/tree/main/Food%20Market%204.0>.

The code is optimised to work with any browser on any operating system. A database still needs to be set up by following the specification in the README file provided within the repo. The readme also gives information regarding the system architecture and connection to the instruments and tools.

The prototype can be tested within any food market, whether retail (e.g.: Municipal Markets or other food hubs) or wholesale (e.g.: So.Ge.Mi. general food market or other food hubs).

Installing and using the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard system requires a Wi-Fi network connection to access dashboard functionalities, as well as the following hardware elements:

- a digital scale;
- a minicomputer;
- a touch screen display;
- an RFID reader (to be connected to the digital scale);
- one or more RFID antennas (to be placed in the stall and/or warehouse);
- a set of boxes with integrated RFID.

5.5 Paris pilot

5.5.1 Online catalogue and Dimension-use prototype – Fab City Grand Paris

Description of functionality

This use case takes place in the temporary event domain (such as fairs and festivals), and its main aim is to discover hidden resources and to give a turn-key solution to the organisations that collect used materials (such as wood) in order to reuse it.

Nowadays, most of the resource centers and circular economy stakeholders specialized in material collection are:

1. manually measuring their materials and
2. manually filling their database, if they have one.

This workflow **generates errors**, is **time consuming** and can **hinder the resource centre's functioning**. Therefore, resource centers often choose not to dedicate time to document materials in stock, in favour of material collection. Consequently, material stocks are “invisible” and/or difficult to access. Actors and actresses that wish to reuse materials for their projects have to visit each resource center to have access to their stock.

This scenario involves two different types of stakeholders: resource centers and the temporary event organizers.

On one hand, the resource centers make an inventory of their incoming materials using Dimension-use. This tool has been developed by WAO Architecture²⁰, and it automates the digitalisation of second-hand materials in resource centers. After digitalisation, the data is uploaded to an online database.

²⁰ <https://wao.paris/>

On the other hand, temporary event organizers browse this online database via WAO's online platform and can order materials from all over the Paris area. They do not need to visit each of the resource centers, as all their materials are now available on the online platform.

Dimension-use is composed by two main parts: a hardware part and a software application. The dimension-use hardware is an open-source device that connects to the Dimension-use application and automatically measures materials. This hardware is customized for resource centers. After measuring the material, the Dimension-use application automates the digitization of the stocks and uploads the data to a unique database, which is shared by all Dimension-use users.

Fab City Grand Paris (FCGP)'s prototype is to synchronize WAO's online database with a REFLOW OS back-end (deployed by FCGP). This allows to produce for each resource contained in the database a material passport, linked to the appropriate actors and processes. In this way stakeholders browsing the Weloop interface have access to all the materials available in their vicinity, as well as their material passport. The material passport can track and trace the resource, as long as the owner of the material registers the events that the material undergoes with the REFLOW OS platform. The users also have access to standardized and comparable information about a wide diversity of second-hand materials. This access allows the users to focus more on their project and less on the material selection, thanks to the standardized and comparable information provided to them.

In short, this prototype gives stakeholders access to a common database with standardized information about the second-hand materials entered through the Dimension-use application, as well as the track and trace tool of REFLOW OS. Stakeholders are therefore able to certify the origin and sources of the materials for their project. Dimension-use specific hardware and software application have been however developed outside the scope of this prototype by WAO Architecture, a start-up incubated by Driven²¹.

Modelling the use case

The figure below depicts the value flow of the second edition of Maison et Objet's²² event in 2021 as the selected use case. According to the Value Flows vocabulary, we can find: agents, in green, economic resources, in blue, and economic events, in grey. Each economic event is linked to the agents that are taking action upon the economic resource. The line labels connecting agents to economic events correspond to the role agents have regarding the corresponding action in the economic event.

During the <consume>/<produce> (represented as "produce" in the figure), the economic resource 'temporary construction' is <consumed> and the economic event <produces> creates a new economic resource: 'wood scrapping', from the previous one.

With the economic event <transfer>, the economic resource 'wood scrapping' changes of both owner and location. As such, two agents, "Event organizer" and "Recovery centre", act upon the economic resource. The former is the provider of the resource, the latter is the receiver.

²¹ <https://drivenbyvolumes.io/>

²² <https://www.maison-objet.com/en/paris>

Once the <transfer> of the economic resource ‘wood scrapping’ happens, the now owner of the economic resource <wood scrapping> digitizes the material through the Dimension-use device that produces a resource record. At this point this data is sent to REFLOW OS. The record contains information about the receiver agent “Recovery centre”, as well as the provider agent “Event Organisation ” and the primary economic resource ‘Temporary construction’. The resource becomes accessible and searchable online.

Because the agent “Event organizer” has initially logged into REFLOW OS using Weloop, and registered the economic resource “Temporary construction”, the prototype identifies and links the newly entered economic resource ‘wood scrapping’ to its source economic resource ‘Temporary construction’, from which it derives.

Once the economic resource “wood scrapping” and “label” is <transferred> to another agent, the continuity of the information available for track and trace depends on the new agent “Makers”.

FIGURE 53: MODEL OF THE MAISON ET OBJET USE CASE IN VALUE FLOWS, CREATED WITH THE GRAPHIC MODELLING TOOL DESCRIBED EARLIER IN THIS DOCUMENT

The following figure (Figure 54) depicts in more details Value Flows concepts that have been used in GraphQL calls to upload the data between Dimension-use and REFLOW OS. The underlined names represent actual types in Value Flows/GraphQL schema. Most graph edges are fields relating one type to another. Also, distinct types use distinct colours, except for Unit/Measure because they are always used together.

FIGURE 54: DETAILED VALUE FLOWS USING A CUSTOM TOOL

Using the prototype

For stakeholders who wish to donate materials from their temporary construction’s dismantlement, they can do so by having them collected by a resource center. In order to find a resource center that can collect the material, they login to the Parisian instance of REFLOW OS, where they create a resource and express their intention to offer it for free. In parallel, a resource center, logged into Weloop, is looking for materials to retrieve.

While browsing the Weloop interface, the resource center finds the offer from the “donor” and decides to retrieve their material. Both actors get in contact and agree to a transfer that is registered in REFLOW OS as an economic event.

Once a resource center has retrieved the material and stored it, it can showcase its new resources online to attract clients. The center automates this process using the Dimension-use application with which it can either semi-automatically or manually scan the materials and enter standard fields identifying the materials.

The standardized fields that have been filled for each material, are automatically published online. The digitized materials are now available both on WAO's online platform and on REFLOW OS.

FIGURE 55: PROTOTYPE OF THE DIMENSION-USE, MOBILE VERSION IN SEMI-AUTOMATIC MODE

Dimension-Use acts like a low-cost 3D scanner for reused materials and custom made for resource centers. The hardware is open source. The hardware repository contains a detailed description of material and technical instructions for installation and deployment, allowing for resource centers the ability to freely reproduce it. However, the software developed by WAO Architecture is not open source and has been developed outside REFLOW, as explained in the introduction.

WAO developed two different versions of the hardware/software: a portable version and a static one, to serve different purposes. The static version is more advanced, as it is the version that has shown to have the best potential.

The user can add manual inputs of the object characteristics to the online database through the interface. The semi-automatic mode is accessible from the interface: the user manually determines the box in which the object is contained. Measurements are automatically made from 2 photos taken on 2 planes (XY and ZX). The error coefficient is 3%-7% for big measurements; superior to 16% for measurements inferior to 7,5 cm. The method for the 3D measurements consists in using 2 cameras, 1 for each plane. The photo displayed above

depicts Dimension-use's mobile version in semi-automatic mode.

Synchronization with REFLOW OS

Once the data about the newly available stock is entered using Dimension-use, it is automatically sent online, and displayed in the online database, on WAO's website. This online database is periodically synchronized with REFLOW OS, by translating Dimension-Use data model into Value Flows. This ensures all the materials lifecycle is recorded and linked in REFLOW OS. As such, Dimension-Use becomes a touchpoint for data to be sent to REFLOW OS.

Dimension-Use focuses on resources that are local to Paris. The idea is that Dimension-Use facilitates data collection for actors of the recycling economy, and REFLOW OS provides data normalization at a broader scale and data discoverability required for a thriving recycling network.

Technical building blocks

In details, the synchronization is performed by calling REFLOW's GraphQL API through an AWS lambda function²³. Lambda functions run periodically, similarly to a cron job²⁴. A cron-based synchronization has been considered the simplest approach compared to event-based ones, both in terms of simplicity and flexibility. The data pipeline takes all the Dimension-Use database entities which changed since the last time it ran and executes the appropriate GraphQL queries and mutations to avoid duplicates.

Back-end: The pilot's back-end is comprised of two parts: one is the Dimension-Use cloud API and database, and the other is the REFLOW OS's project back-end: Bonfire.

The Dimension-Use part consists of a MySQL database and a python HTTP webserver, while Bonfire (described in D2.4 and in the upcoming D2.6) exposes a GraphQL HTTP API interface which is used by the synchronization component described above.

Front-end: The pilot front-end is also divided between the Dimension-Use aspect and the REFLOW OS aspect. Dimension-Use provides a local HTTP web-server for manipulating and executing materials measurements, while this use-case uses Weloop (described in D2.5 and upcoming D2.6) as an interface for Reflow.

Future Implementations

In the future, the online catalogue provided with REFLOW OS will federate information scattered among the multitude of the different reuse networks. Not only does each resource center record a small fraction of their stock's information, but the media of communication greatly varies from one another. The aim of the catalogue is to centralize information on a unique website, without stripping resource centers of their independence towards the platform. Thus, the income of resource centers remains independent from the catalogue as the latter is only a means for the clients to get in touch with the appropriate resource centers. The other added value of the catalogue is the homogenization of the available information for each material.

²³ <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AWSCloudFormation/latest/UserGuide/aws-resource-lambda-function.html>

²⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cron>

The first beta testers for the online catalogue are La Ressourcerie du Cinema²⁵. Later on, the test will be extended to other resource centers to test the federation of different data sources in the online catalogue.

Use of REFLOW OS tools

REFLOW OS acts as a crucial tool for tracing and tracking materials. With the current regulation being billed in France, the need for tracing will soon be compulsory for a wide range of reused materials. On the other hand, the current actors producing scrap wood or by-products from their wood installations are required to track their waste and prove that it will be reused. As such, REFLOW OS linked to our solution provides resource centers, as well as their deposit's owners, with a turnkey solution. Event organizations can easily get in touch with resource centers through the REFLOW OS network of users registered on Weloop and track their materials. Resource centers can easily have access to new deposits, as well as trace the origin and source of their materials to better assess their future possible uses.

Moreover, the blockchain aspect of the material passport ensures the authenticity of the information for stakeholders. In FIGURE 56 below an example of a Material Passport using Weloop:

FIGURE 56: WELOOP - MATERIAL PASSPORT VIEW

Resources

Given the requirement that a user has to enter data using Dimension-Use to test the prototype, using the prototype is limited to users that have the hardware and software parts of Dimension-Use. On the other hand, any user can observe the available economic resources entered via Dimension-use using Weloop.

²⁵ <https://laressourcerieducinema.org/>

Paris' REFLOW OS node is deployed and owned by Fab City Grand Paris. To be able to use the prototype, one can get in touch with Fab City Grand Paris at hello@fabcity.paris, with the subject line "REFLOW OS access".

To have access to the Dimension-Use product, one can get in touch with WAO Architecture. The prototype is currently in one resource center, in Paris.

The code that performs the synchronization between Dimension-use online database and REFLOW OS is hosted at <https://github.com/reflow-project/Paris-pilot/blob/main/du-reflow/>.

5.5.2 Re-label prototype – Ars Longa

Description of functionality

Re-label provides a graphical color-coded label to quantify and qualify the circular practices of workshops working with wood and other materials. It is designed for designers, makers and manufacturers.

The aim of Re-label is to facilitate the creation of communities, bringing together all reuse facilitators, to create an exchange of good practices between them, in order to improve the performance of the labelled workshops and designers. Any improvement in circular practices is reflected in the label scores of the productions.

The Re-label responds to the need for new standards on reuse in product design, furniture, interior design and micro-architecture, to give better awareness to ecological and circular approaches implemented by small associative workshops or by independent designers and manufacturers. It is also a communication tool and a way to promote the manufacturing potential of a territory.

The actors in this scenario are:

- Creative people (designers, artisans, makers)
- Workshop managers
- Communities which gather creative people, workshop managers and actors of the circular economy.
- Final consumers: to see what is hidden behind the production of a product
- Political leaders: who can understand the communities of manufacturers and economic stakeholders

Re-Label is also an online platform that allows public or private organisations, independent designers and makers, to make the reuse policy of a community of actors visible. Re-Label is a tool that facilitates citizen engagement and the weaving of interactions between actors in the same territory.

Designing the labels

The first step in designing the labels was to understand what information to collect, or what questions to ask designers, workshops and communities as beta testers of the label.

The questionnaire we designed consists of two forms: the first part of the form asks to provide simple information about the organisation. The second part of the form is about the production and it is more detailed, especially about reuse and sustainability.

In the first version of the Re-label questionnaire, it was necessary to answer the same questions every month to be able to estimate the evolution of the workshop or the designer over a whole year:

Man-time on re-used material production (conception, production)
Man-time on re-used material management (dismantling, storage, research)
What is the % of re-used materials on the total volume of your productions
How much wood type is available in the workshop for distributed storage
Number of partner structures on recycling activities
Average distance between the recycling material recovery site and the workshop
Average distance between the place of production and the place of exploitation or sale

The designer had to fill out a form to register each production:

name of the designer
name of the maker
Size and number
Size
Number of units
Date and time
Start prod / End prod
Man-time on re-used material production (conception, production, products, space arrangement of the workshop)
Man-time on re-used material management (dismantling, storage, research)
Places
Place of origin - only for reused materials (place of purchase or recovery)
Location of the production
location of the sale
Realisation materials
new material
Re-use material
Realisation
Finishing and post-processing
Number of possible life cycles
Dismountable or not
Storage
Repairable

We decided to simplify the questionnaire by removing the part to be filled out every month, as it required too much work for the workshops and creatives.

The new questionnaire has a simpler organisation part but a more detailed part for the productions. The data requested below will generate a Re-label label to be printed when the object is sold:

1. Presentation
 - a. Name of the project
 - b. Type (object, space, furniture)
 - c. Description
 - d. The designer(s)
 - e. The manufacturing workshop(s)
 - f. The partner structures
2. The materials
 - a. The source of the materials used (suppliers)
 - b. The quality of the materials (treated, responsible...)
 - c. The management of the scraps resulting from the production of the project
 - d. The geographical origin of the main material used
3. Design
 - a. Replicable design
 - b. Contributive design
 - c. Repairable design
 - d. Durability of the design
4. Manufacturing
 - a. The know-how that the project highlights
 - b. Proximity of the production to the use of the product
 - c. The specificity and complexity of the tools used
 - d. The social impact of manufacturing

The picture below (FIGURE 57) shows the point 2, 3 and 4. The bars at the bottom of the picture represent an indicator of spent man-time in management, logistics, handling, design, production, etc.

FIGURE 57

In order to test the graphic translation of the data, we created a prototype of the label in Processing²⁶ to submit it to beta testers (see FIGURE 58 below). This allowed us to determine that we didn't want to rate practices through the label but to encourage an understanding of the creatives' approach through a graphic label. Each colour has a meaning, while the circles allow us to understand the number of processes or actions following the principles of Re-label.

The colour scheme is such that one colour corresponds to open and sustainable design, another to involvement of the project in local manufacturing and short circuit, and third one to commitment in terms of responsible materials. The re-label code is based on the functioning of Truchet's tiles²⁷.

FIGURE 58

²⁶ <https://p5js.org/>

²⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Truchet_tiles

In the example below (FIGURE 59), the green is for responsible and sourced materials, the red is for an open and sustainable production, and the yellow represents a local and social fabrication.

FIGURE 59

The criteria for Re-label were determined through surveying 12 designers and workshops. The variables of the label are based on the real conditions of the workshops and of the creatives' practices.

During the first research period, we wanted to work on different levels of percentages: working time, weight, material research time, on general practice of designers and workshops. While testing the data collection forms, the feedback we received highlighted the lack of time to answer these complex forms. As a result, this led us to simplify the process by focusing on the final product to make sure that the exercise of filling out the form is something quick and straightforward.

Practically, the label is created by a generator. The label generator works with questionnaires that also allow sharing information on the Re-label platform about the actors of Re-label and their projects. The projects are always linked to a project leader (organisation) who is linked to a community.

User story

Thibaut is a freelance designer working in Bagnolet. He works at the Cocoricut workshop based at Morning Coworking. There, he often uses a digital milling machine, a laser cutter, and hand tools to produce his projects. In the workshop, while chatting with the other people working there, he discovers that Cocoricut is referenced on re-label.eu.

By consulting the platform, he discovers not only communities but also inspiring good practices. Thibaut wishes to promote his work but would also especially like to evaluate his responsible approach developed in his projects. He is interested in joining a community and expanding his network, and in having access to certification tools for the objects he creates.

Thibaut fills in the organisation form and provides his personal information. He selects a community to which he belongs, already registered on the platform, the Fab City Store. After the organisation form, where he declared his company, Thibaut fills in a first Production form. The questions are simple and as a designer-manufacturer, he knows his manufacturing process, which allows him to fill in the form in a few minutes.

When Thibaut sells a product, a Re-label label is generated.

FIGURE 60: PROFILE OF DESIGNER JOINING RE-LABEL

In the screenshots below some examples of labels can be seen:

FIGURE 61: THE PRODUCTIONS PAGE REFERENCES ALL THE PROJECTS THAT HAVE BEEN LABELLED

[COMMUNAUTÉS](#) [STRUCTURES](#) [PRODUCTIONS](#) [BONNES PRATIQUES](#) [NOUS CONTACTER](#)

RE-LABEL

UN OUTILS COLLABORATIF QUI RECENSE ET PARTAGE

<p>DES PRODUCTIONS RESPONSABLES</p> <p>Re-Label met en avant des productions responsables et vertueuses qui contribuent au développement d'une nouvelle manière de produire et consommer.</p> <p>Voir les productions</p>	<p>DES STRUCTURES ENGAGÉES</p> <p>Re-Label cartographie les structures qui contribuent et porte ces projets pour valoriser leur démarche collaborative.</p> <p>Voir la carte des structures</p>	<p>DES COMMUNAUTÉES LOCALES</p> <p>Re-Label documente le développement de réseaux de collaborations localisés. Re-Label permet de visualiser l'état des écosystèmes sur les différents territoires.</p> <p>Voir les communautés</p>
--	--	--

<p>A PROPOS</p> <p>Le projet RE-label est porté à Paris dans le cadre du projet ReFlow, par l'équipe de Ars Longa. Si vous avez des questions, des suggestions ou autre, contactez nous directement à info@arslonga.fr</p>	<p>COMMUNAUTÉS</p> <p>Liste des communautés Proposer une communauté</p>	<p>STRUCTURES</p> <p>Carte des structures Référencer la votre</p>	<p>PRODUCTIONS</p> <p>Portfolio Labelliser un projet</p>	<p>CONTACT</p> <p>Nous contacter Github</p>
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FIGURE 62: RE-LABEL HOMEPAGE EXPLAINS THE AIM OF THE RE-LABEL INITIATIVE, MENTIONING THE PARTNERS.

FIGURE 63: THE WHOLE COMMUNITY IS ACCESSIBLE ON THE ORGANISATION PAGE WITH A MAP SHOWING THE DIFFERENT HUBS CREATED BY THE LABELLED ORGANISATIONS

During sales or exhibition events, we asked several consumers if they knew about the label, if they had an interest in buying a labelled object, and what added value they found in it.

Consumers are often informed about the label through a labelled object and through the communication made by the designers about their labelling.

For the consumer, it is important to be aware of the efforts made by designers to produce responsible and sustainable objects. Consumers express the desire to question their way of consuming and buying objects. The data collected through the product forms and visually shown by the labels allow create an added value for the purchased object, because consumers gain a better understanding of the creation process and the importance of reuse in the project.

Technical building blocks

The current prototype is built on 3 main building blocks:

- The **front-end**: The front end is built with serverless technologies with Next.js²⁸ and React²⁹. Next.js allows generating static website in order to optimize speed and Search Engine Optimisation. Next.js also automatically builds new pages when the back-end changes.
- The **back-end**: The back-end is built with a sequin³⁰ instance, replicating an Airtable³¹ database as a Postgres database. This allows for structured queries and overcoming Airtable API's limitations but still

²⁸ <https://nextjs.org/>

²⁹ <https://reactjs.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.sequin.io/>

³¹ <https://www.airtable.com/>

gaining its ease of use to create, update and delete data if needed. This is especially useful at this stage as there are many trials and errors.

- The **hosting**: The web app is hosted on Vercel³², allowing for native hosting of Next.js apps, with SSR (Server-Side Rendering), SSG (Static Site Generation), CSR (Client-Side Rendering) and ISR (Incremental Static Regeneration).

As soon as a production is labelled on the Re-label platform, the data is transmitted to REFLOW OS using its GraphQL API. Weloop then can display the link to the material passport (an example of this has been shown in the previous prototype's section).

In order to implement the connection between Re-label and REFLOW OS, we first modelled our use case according to the Value Flows vocabulary (see picture below). Since we were planning to connect to the REFLOW OS instance deployed by the dimension-use use case (described in the previous section), the structure of the different agents, resources and actions were jointly agreed upon in order to ensure compatibility.

After testing with a temporary staging server to experiment with our flows without any consequences for the real production server, the production Re-label app is planned to interact directly with the production instance of REFLOW OS hosted by FCGP.

³² <https://vercel.com/>

FIGURE 64: MODEL OF THE USE-CASE ACCORDING TO VALUE FLOWS³³

Use of REFLOW OS tools

Currently, Re-label traces and qualifies the efforts spent on creating a sustainable project (second-hand materials, social impact...). At the moment, every time a project is labelled, the data and information about the resources it uses, and the actors involved are automatically pushed to REFLOW OS, in order to store them.

³³ A high-res version of this picture is at: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Paris-pilot/blob/main/relabel/fig/Frame%201.jpg>

Once the project is labelled, a material passport is generated in REFLOW OS and a reference is directly linked on the Re-label website. This way, every labelled project can link to its full historical data on REFLOW OS.

On the long term, to facilitate the labelling process, we will couple Re-label with the material catalogue developed by Fab City Grand Paris (described in the previous section). This will allow projects using the catalogue to reuse the data of the materials in the catalogue as input for the information required by the labelling process.

Re-label is a local initiative. Using REFLOW OS has the potential to connect to a larger network with a greater diversity of actors from other countries. Having the same values of being decentralized and distributed confidence tools, Re-label and REFLOW OS can work together.

Resources

All code developed is open-sourced and hosted on a public repo on github: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Paris-pilot/tree/main/relabel>.

The prototype is up and functional at <https://re-label.eu/>. The instance deployed can be used by anyone. If someone wanted to deploy its own instance, they would need:

- A correctly structured Airtable database (duplicable [here](#))
- A Vercel account to deploy his instance.
- A fork of the current repo.

5.6 Vejle pilot

5.6.1 REMA 1000's candy boxes

Description of functionality

This scenario focuses on the food retail chain REMA 1000's usage of plastic containers (PP/Polypropylene) to transport self-serve mixed candy from manufacturer to retail stores. Currently, once these plastic boxes are emptied, they are shipped off for incineration. The Vejle pilot use case aims to change this into a closed-up re-use loop. For context, it is worth mentioning that REMA 1000 is publicly known for being a leading sustainability-focused retail chain.

This scenario includes a broad range of actors that populate the full width of the value chain of the use case in question:

- **REMA 1000:** National-scale retail store (supermarket) with 360 stores across Denmark. It is part of Reitan Group, which has approximately 1900 stores in the Nordic countries.
- **Superfoss:** Manufacturer of candy box plastic containers.
- **Cloetta:** Manufacturer of candy that is filled into the plastic containers.

- **Aage Vestergaard Larsen:** Waste management company that handles the candy boxes once used at REMA 1000 stores.
- **Miljøstyrelsen:** Ecosystem stakeholder which seeks to optimize waste management and boost circular economy as part of a government political agenda and mandate.
- **Marius Pedersen:** Logistics company that handles transportation of candy boxes between stakeholders, both empty and full boxes.
- **Resource center Vejle:** Vejle Municipality's new ambitious waste management center, which on one hand handles incineration but on the other hand puts resources into optimizing waste management and minimizing waste in general (including putting resources into circular economy boosting experiments).
- **Various waste transportation companies:** Alongside Marius Pedersen A/S and Aage Vestergaard A/S, as listed above, there are several unnamed logistical subcontractor companies involved. However, they are to be considered more like an "event", rather than an actor, as they are engaged ad hoc and are often replaced.

Each actor naturally has individual needs that this pilot scenario addresses, but several needs overlap several actors. The following have been identified as the major ones:

- Economic incentive, save money on re-use when scaled: simply by not having to buy new candy boxes.
- Minimize storage and stockpile cost, since by re-using boxes, they no longer need to be kept on stock for as long.
- Branding value, by being able to tell stories to customers and the general public about sustainability efforts being made.
- Sustainability agenda - varies from actor to actor - but boils down to a rising consumer demand for sustainable business.
- Need for closer collaboration across the value chain: this initiative is an opportunity to forge closer relationships with other actors.

The prototype closes the loop for plastic waste by visualizing a circular loop of the value chain for the candy boxes (PP) in question.

It does so by using two components in unison: The REFLOW OS software and a workshop format built around a playful board game. The latter serves to initiate the collaboration of the stakeholders, by having them create a visualization of the value chain, as well as to collaborate on brainstorming new ideas for ways to create circular loops to replace the current linear flow.

The visualization of the value chain looks like this³⁴ (see also zoomed-in versions further below):

³⁴ A high-res version of this figure is at: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Vejle-pilot/blob/main/fig/Frame%201.jpg>

- More tests of the prototype in different scenarios are being scheduled: one with SDU (South Danish University) to take place in Q2 2022, in which it will be tested in an educational setting. Another one was held at the Danish Design Center in February 2022, where the organisation's key facilitators are gathered to review and evaluate the documentation, supporting materials and flow of the prototype. Feedback will be incorporated to improve the pedagogy of the materials.
- Lastly, the prototype is intended to be tested as a commercial offering after the conclusion of Reflow. Both Danish Design Center and private sector consultancy Spraengfarlig ApS are planning to offer the service as a product on market terms (as also referenced in D7.5 as a business case).

The prototype allows stakeholders to test in advance by sourcing existing data to estimate and simulate the future potential of circular loops. And they can do so even without accessing real data, if there is reluctance against sharing data. In that case simulated data can be used to simulate materials flows.

The prototype consists of two major components: REFLOW OS software and a board game to be used in a workshop with all stakeholders.

The stakeholders are invited to a half-day workshop where they play the board game to map out the full complexity of the value chain, as well as to collaborate and brainstorm about new circular loops that could be implemented by working together. The intention is to create several ideas (suggestions) and then pick 2 or 3 to explore further after the workshop.

It is worth noting that the workshop serves an additional purpose as well, which is more of a social component: namely to bring stakeholders together to learn to know each other better. Oftentimes they have never all been in the same room together, and by meeting in a big group they create a new, shared vision for ambitious experimentation. This mission and alignment would have been extremely hard to achieve without the workshop and the playfulness of the board game.

Next the visualization is transferred to the REFLOW OS software. This is easy because the board game uses the Value Flows vocabulary. The transfer is done by the facilitator (in this case the Vejle Pilot Reflow team).

Lastly, by showcasing the new digital version of the value chain to the stakeholders, as now available in the REFLOW OS software, talks can be initiated with the stakeholders about potential implementation of the software in the scaling of the circular loop creation efforts. Scaling complex efforts like making significant changes in the value chain is always difficult, because it includes changing deeply rooted logistic modes. This process becomes significantly easier by taking a point of departure in a successful prototype that shows the feasibility of the effort. This allows all actors in the value chain to see a proof of concept. Hopefully that will help the conversation move from a focus on the whether the effort is feasible to one where the focus is on removing the barriers for scaling.

In the following we show the entire value chain visualization³⁵ according to Value Flows and zoomed-in versions.

³⁵ A high-res figure is available at: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Vejle-pilot/blob/main/fig/Frame%20202.jpg>

FIGURE 66

Zoom-in on the part of the value chain visualization that shows the current linear path for PP plastic containers (boxes) from manufacturing to incineration³⁶:

FIGURE 67

³⁶ A high-res figure is available at: <https://github.com/reflow-project/Vejle-pilot/blob/main/fig/Frame%203.jpg>

Zoom-in on part of the value chain visualization that shows the new circular loop in which the containers are not incinerated, but chopped into pellets and returned to the manufacturer for re-use in the manufacturing of new candy plastic containers:

FIGURE 68

The following (FIGURE 69) presents the documentation we created. The next picture shows the frontpage of value chain board game instructions and a visualization of the game pieces used to populate the board game as part of the workshop:

FIGURE 69

The next picture (FIGURE 70) shows sample pages from documentation rulebook explaining the participants (1) what a value chain visualization could look like and (2) the game pieces and a sample board made from a brown paper roll.

FIGURE 70

Screenshots from adding data in Bonfire + setting up material passport loop (current prototype in Bonfire). First step is defining the stakeholders (agents):

FIGURE 71

Then define the resource that takes part in the flow under attention (in this case PP Pellets):

FIGURE 72

Then insert the events of the flow that involve the resource:

FIGURE 73

Technical building blocks

This prototype uses a version of REFLOW OS running on a local instance (a virtual machine with Debian 11.2.0 on VirtualBox), using REFLOW OS native interface Phoenix as shown in the previous screenshots.

The Value Flows has been used extensively to describe material flows and its concepts have been transferred to the above-mentioned board game to ensure smooth alignment between the two.

Testing

The REFLOW Vejle Pilot has team has been working directly with the stakeholders to test:

- Tested Value Flows in WeLoop (syntax/architecture) as tool to test the logic between board game and OS.
- Tested in the workshop (using the board game) if the logic works with the stakeholders.

The stakeholders that have been involved in the testing are:

- REMA 1000
- Cloetta
- Miljøstyrelsen
- RCV - waste handler Municipality

From the testing, these are some of the reflections that came up during evaluation of the experience:

- There is great value in using data for evaluation: it creates a foundation for finding the best circular loop before trying to implement it. Even if you do not have complete data available, you may still be able to find an indication of the plausibility of the experiment.
- Tracking materials through a lifetime is highly valuable, and currently very rare: getting data backing for actual reuse and recycling allows you to be able to indicate exact amounts, even at scale. This makes up a tremendous selling point in getting all of the value chain of actors on board.
- This process allows for the uncovering of business potentials for business, especially as it relates to scaling: by testing the micro-scale using the board game, you can validate the entire approach, and then move towards scaling the effort using REFLOW OS.
- There is a huge difference between wanting to create circular loops (having good intentions) and actually implementing the change. Many grave obstacles hinder the way, including convincing all relevant stakeholders in the value chain to take part, so it is necessary to be aware of how to communicate and work in a way that will convince all stakeholders to get involved. In essence, to create a shared mission across the value chain's actors.
- Perhaps the greatest value of the combination of the board game and REFLOW OS is that it allows the stakeholders to create a technical prototype without any of them having to give access to data from their systems. Getting access to data is highly complicated because it requires lots of trust. Example: The waste handler in the REMA1000 prototype, Aage Vestergaard A/S, said at the workshop that they would be willing to share a data dump, but 3 months later they still hadn't released any because of push-back from other places in the organization. Therefore, being able to test a prototype using micro-scale, constructed data is a great validation as a first step.

Resources

The Circular Value Chain Game has been published, together with its documentation, at the following webpage: <https://ddc.dk/tools/circular-value-chain-game/>.

6 Lessons learnt and Conclusions

This deliverable presents quite a broad spectrum of technical solutions implemented within the scope of T5.4. It is evident that having six pilot cities, with sometimes more than one pilot (partner) per city, and a total of 10 different use cases, has resulted in a considerable diversity in approaches, level of technical development, and focus of interests. Some pilots have advanced more in the technological development, using technology as the main enabler of circular solutions, while for other pilots, technology has been a means to start or promote the discussion on circular economy.

Each prototype has been developed with a particular local focus specific to each pilot city; nevertheless, aiming at replicability of the tools as much as possible, the software in almost all cases has been released as open-source (with AGPLv3 licence) in the GitHub project repository³⁷, together with the documentation on how to use it, as indicated in each pilot section of this deliverable. This has not been done (yet) in the cases where discussions about exploitation of the software was still not finalized.

At the same time, as it has been described in this deliverable, the WP2 tools the pilots were supposed to use were evolving constantly due to the extreme innovative technological path Reflow has chosen, namely to adopt and contribute to an evolving standard (Value Flows), for which no stable software was yet available at the start of the project. This has led to several contributions from Reflow to Value Flows, as it has been discussed in this document, as well as to providing necessary feedback for the development of REFLOW OS WP2 tools. Both results are particularly important considering that RELOW OS is a core component of the REFLOW's Legacy, as described in D7.5. However, it has also caused difficulties because pilots could not be pointed to extensive documentation and fully working tools.

These factors have led to the phased approach explained in this deliverable, namely, to test incrementally with a few pilots in order to establish a short path of feedback between pilots testing the tools on one hand, and Value Flows community and software developers on the other hand. Such an approach slightly resembles the iterative approach adopted by Agile development, only that the latter happens mostly within a single team, while in REFLOW's case there were six (and more) teams.

While each of the pilots have had their share of lessons learnt throughout their individual journeys, as reported in each of the pilot's respective sections in the deliverable, there is also a general lesson to be learned from REFLOW. The difficulties caused in REFLOW due to having many different teams using tools that were in stages of evolution has generated the lesson for future teams similar to REFLOW's situation to adopt a phased approach. This phased approach, as already described in the deliverable, eases the development path of as many teams as possible.

³⁷ <https://github.com/reflow-project>

7 Appendix

7.1 Contribution and discussion with the Value Flows community

<https://gitter.im/valueflows/welcome?at=613e4c444c7be06b79b44b76>

Lynn Foster @fosterlynn Sep 12 2021 20:51

@sbocconi I just wanted to let you know that we did add "pack" and "unpack" to the vocab, thanks very much for the discussion! I know you are hesitant to use something new because of the code already written for your project. But just in case....

<https://valueflo.ws/introduction/flows.html#actions>

<https://valueflo.ws/examples/ex-production.html#pack-unpack>

<https://github.com/dyne/reflow-os/issues/3#issuecomment-975658577>

fosterlynn commented on 22 Nov 2021

It's just seems to make sense to give things the same name when you are working together to get insight into the flow of resources.

@ocataco thanks, seems like a valid (and nice) use case, just not one VF has run into. You mean the same ID too, I assume, meaning it is the same resource instance in the software. (Just to note for future reference, you can follow the flows of resources in either case, by following them through the input-process-output and transfer activities, irrespective of agents and locations. But still, good use case.)

What is you all's preference? You could use transfer event atLocation to change the resource currentLocation, if you don't need atLocation for its original purpose, which was requested by people who thought they might want to track distances for climate accounting, but afaik have not yet done so. Or we could add a property to event only for explicitly changing the resource currentLocation, if you want at this moment in your development. If we add it, when `move` is fixed, it could use the new field.

To me, it has become abundantly clear and we should go ahead and add the field and fix the hack, from the VF point of view. Getting it into the graphql spec, and using it in projects, can be coordinated as needed, and at projects' convenience. Opinions welcome. I'll put together a MR/PR in VF though, to get things moving, some time today.

fosterlynn commented on 24 Nov 2021

Added a property in VF called `toLocation` on `EconomicEvent`, that can be used to update `currentLocation` on the `EconomicResource`. Not yet in the graphql spec, probably not yet showing in the website gitbook.

https://lab.allmende.io/valueflows/valueflows/-/merge_requests/663/diffs

ocataco commented on 25 Nov 2021

That sounds like a very nice addition, thanks Lynn!

Added a property in VF called `toLocation` on `EconomicEvent`, that can be used to update `currentLocation` on the `EconomicResource`. Not yet in the graphql spec, probably not yet showing in the website gitbook.

https://lab.allmende.io/valueflows/valueflows/-/merge_requests/663/diffs

7.2 Cluj-Napoca Retrofit Kit technical specifications

7.2.1 Smart metering system with 869 MHz band radio communication

System description

The smart metering system takes the consumption data from several points of the beneficiary's electricity network and transmits it to a central point, which exposes it on an interface to be processed by an external data centralization system.

The data is taken from the electricity meters through an RS485 interface by the communicators and transmitted using a wireless communication protocol to a central equipment, gateway, which exposes them on a standardized interface to an external data centralization system.

By using a radio communication protocol, the independence of the system from the interferences appeared in the electricity network is ensured and the costs with the mobile data subscriptions to a third party supplier are eliminated.

The communicators form a mesh network, in which each node in the network can take data from a neighbor to relay it to the gateway.

The intelligent measurement system consists of:

- 10 pcs of mono-phase meter with digital consumption recording and exposure of consumption registers via RS485 interface. The meters used are produced by Noark and have all the metrological approvals to be used in Romania.
- 10 pcs of Communicator with radio transmission in the 868 MHz frequency band standardized at EU level by decision 2017/1483 and in Romania by RO-IR 01. Supply voltage: 12V direct current.
- Equipment that manages the network of communicators called gateways. It also has the role of processing the data and exposing it on a standard interface to an external data centralization system. The data is displayed using an RJ45 ethernet interface or a 3G modem. Supply voltage: 230V alternating current.
- Network management software.

7.2.2 COMPONENT A: lighting modernization

7.2.2.1 Lighting fixtures: 145 pcs

- Power supply: Constant current electronic driver
- Rated voltage 230 V ~
- Nominal frequency 50 Hz
- Luminous efficiency 95... 115 lm / W
- Power factor (λ) > 0.95
- Total harmonic distortions <15%
- Protection class I, II
- LED color (neutral white) 4000 K
- Color rendering index (CRI) > 80

- Lifespan of sources (L80B10) @ 50,000 h
- Optics / material: polycarbonate, polymethacrylate diffuser
- Protection IP20, IP66
- Impact resistance IK02, IK08
- Ambient temperature max. + 50 ° C
- Dedicated luminaires for sheet metal - 500 lx according to SR EN 12464 I

Required works:

- Disassembly of existing luminaires: 145 pcs.
- Installation of lighting fixtures: 145 pcs.

7.2.2.2 Motion sensors: 40 pcs

- 230V / 50Hz
- IP20
- 1 contact ND
- Maximum detection angle 120 °
- Maximum detection distance 8m

Required works:

- Mounting motion sensors: 40 pcs;

7.2.3 COMPONENT B: Electrical panels

- 1 pc. General panel;
- 5 pcs. Secondary distribution boards;
- Apparent / buried installation in existing niches;
- Degree of protection: min. IP20
- Rated voltage 230/400 V ~
- Nominal frequency 50 Hz
- Ambient temperature max. + 25 ° C
- Contains PE + N concentration bars
- In accordance with RoHS and WEEE directives

Necessary works:

- Identification of existing circuits
- Identify conductor sections and choose the appropriate protections
- Design and configuration of new panels
- Dismantling existing panels: 1 pc. General panel + 5 pcs. Distribution boards secondary

7.2.4 COMPONENT C: mounting smart sockets

7.2.4.1 Sockets: 16 pcs

Power supply: 230 V

Maximum amperage 16 A

Protection: IP 30

RF signal: ZigBee Pro HA 1.2.

Schuko socket type

7.2.4.2 Gateway 9 pcs

Power supply: 5 V DC, via USB cable

RF signal: ZigBee 2.4 Ghz, HA 1.2

Operating temperature: 0 + 50 ° C

7.3 Milan Botto technical specifications

These are the electronic specifications of the Botto device, starting from the bill of materials for the electronic device:

Part	Value	Device
BUTTON	PIN-HEADER-02X1GROUND	PIN-HEADER-02X1GROUND
ENC		PIN-HEADER-03X1THRU-254
IRL540NPBF	MOSFET-N-IRL540NPBFBENDED-SHORTEST	MOSFET-N-IRL540NPBFBENDED-SHORTEST
R	1k	RESISTOR
RST	PIN-HEADER-02X1GROUND	PIN-HEADER-02X1GROUND
SPKR	PIN-HEADER-02X1GROUND	PIN-HEADER-02X1GROUND
SV1		PIN-HEADER-04X01
U\$1	RESISTOR	RESISTOR
U\$2	POWER-JACK	POWER-JACK
U\$3	ESP32-S2-SAOLA-1	ESP32-S2-SAOLA-1
U\$4	RESISTOR	RESISTOR
U\$5	100	RESISTOR
U\$6	CAPACITOR-POLARIZEDCAP-DIAM-8.3MM-H-12MM-BENT	CAPACITOR-POLARIZEDCAP-DIAM-8.3MM-H-12MM-BENT
U\$7		PIN-HEADER-07X1
U\$8	DIODE	DIODE

U\$9	TRIMMER	TRIMMER
U\$11		PIN-HEADER-07X1
U\$13	CAPACITOR-POLARIZEDCAP-DIAM-8.3MM-H-12MM-BENT	CAPACITOR-POLARIZEDCAP-DIAM-8.3MM-H-12MM-BENT
U\$14	100u	CAPACITOR-POLARIZEDCAP-DIAM-6.5MM-H11.3MM-BENT-FLIP

THE BILL OF MATERIALS

Followed by the scheme of the PCB for the electronic device, designed with Eagle³⁸:

And finally, the layout of the 2-layer PCB for the electronic device, also designed with Eagle:

³⁸ <https://www.autodesk.com/products/eagle/overview>

